

Asian Journal of Religious Studies

“The Lord is truly among us.”

March-June 2018

Vol 63/2-3

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Five Years of Pope Francis

Asian Journal for Religious Studies (AJRS) is a pastoral journal for Christian leaders. It is a bimonthly published from the Papal Seminary, Pune 411014, containing inspiring and brief articles beneficial for Christian leaders.

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Printed at: Kunal Offset, Pune
Typeset at: Papal Seminary Centenary Computer Centre
Publisher: Kuruvilla Pandikattu, Papal Seminary

Subscriptions may be sent either by M.O. or D.D. If sent by cheque, please add ₹ 15 as bank commission. Annual Subscription Rate: ₹ 150 (in India); \$ 5 (in Asia); \$/ Euro 12 (in Europe & America)

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ISSN 2249-1503

“Hagan lio,” Pope Francis told a crowd of millions at World Youth Day in Rio de Janeiro in 2013, “Make some noise,” and there is no question that this pontificate has done just that, notes *America: The Jesuit Review*.

Jorge Bergoglio’s own experiences have molded him to be “an outspoken pope of the poor, the marginalized and the victims of a throwaway culture. He has bluntly rejected the wealth and trappings of his office, and the simple gestures that have accompanied this conviction will be the enduring symbols of his pontificate.” Francis has intensified his predecessor Benedict XVI’s strong condemnations of war, an unfettered market and growing economic disparity; he has also offered a blunt but welcome prophetic voice to the world.

In five years, Francis has produced three landmark documents. First came his apostolic exhortation, “The Joy of the Gospel” (“*Evangelii Gaudium*,” 2013), in which he sketched out his vision of a church whose strengths and resources should “be suitably channeled for the evangelization of today’s world rather than for her self-preservation” (No. 27). It was followed soon after by “*Laudato Si*” (2015). While widely received as a call for environmental protections and a critique of consumerism, the encyclical is also one of the most important social justice encyclicals in history. “Everything is related,” Pope Francis wrote. We cannot affirm the rights of humanity while denying the dignity of our environmental home; we cannot abort or euthanize or marginalize unwanted humans as if they were trash; and we cannot

trash the planet in the pursuit of wealth or ease or misbegotten notions of freedom, notes America.

More controversial was Francis' post-synodal exhortation on the family, "The Joy of Love" (*Amoris Laetitia*, 2016). That exhortation, which looked at a broad range of topics related to human love, also opened up the possibility for those who are divorced and remarried to return to the sacraments under certain conditions. That pastoral concession has drawn the loudest cries: affirmations from many living and ministering in difficult pastoral situations and vigorous criticism from those who charge that the pope is contradicting the doctrine of the church.

Pope Francis wowed the world but, five years on, is in troubled waters, writes *The Guardian*. It sums up: "He entered office on a wave of energy but, as discontent grows over his attitude to abuse scandals, Francis faces opposition on all sides."

This litany of lights and shadows speaks to a larger matter: the personal goal that Francis seems to have set for his papacy. His critics are certainly right about one thing: He does indeed seek "to change the church," in its orientation to the contemporary world. The church is "not a catalogue of prohibitions" to be enforced, Pope Benedict XVI reminded us, nor is it an elite club for the saved. As Pope Francis said before the conclave in which he was elected, the church must go out of itself to proclaim fully the invitation to join in Christ's mission of salvation and redemption. Five years into this ground-breaking papacy, there is much more noise to be made.

We are happy to bring out two volumes to celebrate five years of Pope's joyful and challenging presence. The first one, "Pope Francis: Hi Impact on and Relevance for the Church and Society," brings together 27 Indian thinkers to reflect on the Pope's message. The second one, "Francis Effect" includes 51 authors reflecting on Pope Francis' 51 insights. This Indian contribution contains appreciative messages from the Apostolic Nuncio and all the four cardinals and about 20 bishops.

The Editor

Mar-June 2018

Call to Evangelise

S. Sekar Sebastin

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"Evangelizing, proclaiming Jesus, gives us joy. In contrast, egoism makes us bitter, sad and depresses us. Evangelizing uplifts us." – Pope Francis

Evangelization is a mandate received directly from Jesus as he exhorted "Go, therefore, and make disciples of all nations, baptizing them in the name of the Father, and of the Son, and of the Holy Spirit..." (Mat. 28:19). The Second Vatican Council affirmed this, declaring that the Church is "missionary by her very nature." This proclamation or evangelization gives us real joy. This uplifts us with personal and spiritual renewal, witnessing to others, and the transformation of society and culture, service to the poor and marginalized, and engagement in politics. The evangelization puts forward three basic questions:

What to Evangelize?

To evangelize is nothing but to proclaim the Gospel of Jesus Christ and the good news of his Incarnation, life, Passion, death and Resurrection. In his Apostolic Exhortation *Evangelii Nuntiandi*, Pope Paul VI says: "Thus it has been possible to define evangelization in terms of proclaiming Christ to those who do not know Him, of preaching, of catechetics, of conferring Baptism and the other sacraments." This goes hand-in-hand with the element of transmission of the Christian Faith which consists primarily in proclaiming

Jesus Christ in order to lead others to faith in him. From the beginning, the first disciples burned with the desire to proclaim Christ: ‘We cannot but speak of what we have seen and heard.’ (1Jn 1:1-4). Thus, the proclamation of the Gospel finds joy in having a singular goal namely, to introduce people to the Person of Jesus Christ.

Who to Evangelize?

The responsibility of evangelization does not fall on only the consecrated persons. But the entire Church is called to evangelize, for the Church is “by her nature missionary since, according to the

Far from being a dreaded burden, evangelization should come from everyone as a desire for all to be saved, love for Christ and the recognition of the dignity and value of every person.

plan of the Father, she has as her origin the mission of the Son and the Holy Spirit” (LG 33). As the Father sent the Son and the Son sent the Spirit, so, the Triune God sends the Church to “make men share in the communion between the Father and the Son in their Spirit of Love” (CCC 850). This is a participation in the prophetic mission that each Catholic receives at baptism. It takes place in the ordinary activities and circumstances of life like at home, in the work place, at school, and everywhere. Far from being a dreaded burden, evangelization should come from everyone as a desire for all to be saved, love for Christ and the recognition of the dignity and value of every person.

How to Evangelize?

The third question recalls the words of St. Francis of Assisi, “Preach the gospel always; if necessary, use words”. Pope

Paul VI mentions that “this question of ‘how to evangelize’ is permanently relevant, because the methods of evangelizing vary according to the different circumstances of time, place and culture” (*Evangelii Nuntiandi* 40). An essential form of evangelization is witness in both words and deeds. As St John Paul II noted in *Redemptoris Missio* (No 42:1), “People today put more trust in witnesses than in teachers, in experience than in teaching, and in life and actions than in theories.” In addition, other means of evangelization include preaching (both within and outside of liturgical celebrations), which Paul VI says is “an important and very adaptable instrument of evangelization” (*EN* 43), catechesis, and mass media.

Ultimately, there must be a recognition that evangelization is a great responsibility that bears great rewards. “Woe to me,” St Paul lamented, “if I do not preach the Gospel” (1 Cor. 9:16). “Faith is strengthened,” St John Paul II exclaimed, “when it is given to others” (*Redemptoris Missio* 2.3). We who have been given much by Jesus Christ are asked, in turn, to give the good news to others. Evangelization, thus, entails real joy and inner happiness. Evangelisation cannot be pursued by the persons who are obsessed with self and egoistic in tendency. Egoism cannot find a place in the process of evangelisation. Because, egoism makes us bitter, sad, and depresses us. Can we completely be relieved of egoistic tendency?

Transforming the Selfish Human Nature

Egoism is part and parcel of human nature. Anybody who is involved in the ministry of evangelisation is also infected with this human tendency. Jeremy Bentham (1748-1832), an English gentleman, philosopher, eccentric and social reformer holds that human is naturally selfish. According to

him, “to obtain the greatest portion of happiness for himself is the object of every rational being. Every man is nearer to himself than he can be to any other man.” Behind every act of selfless service, there is some selfish aim. The principle of self preference stands at the base of all human motivation.

The English Philosopher Thomas Hobbes (1588 – 1679) also holds that human nature seeks only that which pleases him/her and is delightful to himself/herself. When

When there is a transmission from egoism to altruism in human nature, then the ministry of evangelisation becomes authentic and brings real joy and uplifts us.

there is a transmission from egoism to altruism in human nature, then the ministry of evangelisation becomes authentic and brings real joy and uplifts us.

References

- Ad Gentes* (Vatican II’s Decree on the Church’s Missionary Activity)
Evangelii Nuntiandi (On Evangelization in the Modern World) Paul VI (1975)
Gaudium et Spes (Vatican II’s Pastoral Constitution on the Church in the Modern World)
Lumen Gentium (Vatican II’s Dogmatic Constitution on the Church)

To be People of True Dialogue

Princy Joseph

Lucknow

Let me start with a question: If you are a follower of Christ, what do you think is a quality you particularly like about him? Is it something he did or something about the kind of person he seems to us, through the many accounts?

If you’re not a Christian, then I ask that you apply the same question to whoever it is that you follow/worship/honour...

Whatever your answer, it is something valuable, something you have drawn from your truest, deepest experience of life. I hope you can make it your meditation, something that inspires you.

As for me, one of the things that always strikes me as amazing and perhaps something I can’t say I fully understand is that this historically real person, whose coming was variously predicted and later recorded, whose personhood, many believe to be fully human and fully God...that this person came and comes (for those who believe) to be with us and meet us where we are, where we are in terms of our mental ability, emotional state, spiritual maturity....

Of course, life happens and it’s not always straight forward and predictable. And this ‘meeting’ between God & not-God people can look very different for each of us and at different points in our individual lives.

Another question: Which is the most important relationship

in your life? What about this relationship makes it important for you? Is it something about the person maybe? Or some value it adds to your life?

Again, while I am very curious to know your answer, whatever it is, I believe it could be very telling of not just the obvious fact but also more; I think it could be somewhat telling of you, your values and priorities, what might be deeply satisfying for you and what might be frustrating. I hope again that the truth of this may in some way enrich you.

Going back to the quality of Christ, a quality that strikes me as unique (of a person and more so of a God-person), is the ability to reach out and talk to people unlike him. A few things that lead me to think this – in his God-ness & in his sinless-ness, he is most unlike any of us. In addition, scripture and other accounts tell us that considering Jesus' social standing in those times, Jesus actively interacted with those unlike him- both those more powerful than him and many who were less.

Jesus was able to use his full person when interacting with people and situations of various shades. He interacted with truth, sometimes with questions in reply to questions, sometimes with stories, some-

times with healing, sometimes with exasperation, sometimes with a blessing.... It's hard to box Jesus' interaction type as wholly soft or hard; we can be sure that it was true to the reality of the people and situation- dove-like sometimes and serpent-like at others.

It's hard to box Jesus' interaction type as wholly soft or hard; we can be sure that it was true to the reality of the people and situation- dove-like sometimes and serpent-like at others

This comes as an unusual and hope-giving quality, much needed, given that our world- the big world and our personal worlds, demand such a range of responses, and for a Christian, it can many times be challenging/confusing as to what is the appropriate Christian response to something – to wars near us and those far away, injustice in our homes to that in other homes etc.

Dialogue, the ability to keep and relate in a relationship, whether between countries or people, on fair, true and grounds of genuinely desiring mutual good and long-term interest of the relationship....is something that Jesus demonstrates throughout the accounts of his time on earth. This doesn't mean always giving in to the demands of the other side, nor does it mean trying to sugar-coat facts for personal gain or to live in denial of faults or hurts caused to us whether by family, colleague or friend. '...to speak the truth in love' seems like a neat principle given to us, for truth and dialogue based relationships. Jesus was God so perhaps he didn't need to fear losing anything when he 'spoke the truth in love...'. The same accounts tell us that he did experience agony and ultimately was crucified for the life he led and the truths he spoke.

Is this easy? Heck no. Those who have tried dialogue will know this. It often involves loss of popularity, loss of favour to dialogue like this. Like many other teachings of Jesus, this too challenges us to take the narrow but truly needed path. And like in all things, simply and truly said, his grace is available, nay needed for us to dialogue and have relationships based on truth and love.

The Figure of David in 1& 2 Samuel

Thomas Karimundackal, SJ
Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth, Pune

More than with any other character in OT, Israel is fascinated by David, deeply attracted to him, bewildered by him and occasionally embarrassed by him. On the one hand, scholars like John McKenzie characterize David as a “bloodthirsty oversexed bandit.” About the same David, Samuel Terrien says, “the purity of David’s faith assumed a quality of elegance which has often gone unnoticed in modern times.” We may wonder whether McKenzie and Terrien are reading the same story about the same man. The relevant assertion about David, which recurs throughout the books of 1& 2 Samuel, is “Yahweh was with him.” This is the theological leitmotif of the apology of David, and the decisive influence of Yahweh’s special favour for David runs throughout the narrative.

The books of Samuel present a highly complex portrait of David who wears many faces in his story: on the one hand we have a shepherd (1 Sam 16:1-13), skilled in fine-arts (1 Sam 16:14-23) and knows how to protect his sheep from the lion or the bear, since he is vigilant, attentive and caring (1 Sam 17:32-37). He is a man of valour, a warrior, prudent in speech, and a man of good presence (1 Sam 16:18). He recognizes his weakness and mistakes (2 Sam 12:13; 24:10, 17).

“Yahweh is always” with him (1 Sam 16:13, 18; 18:12, 14, 28; 2 Sam 5:10; 7:9). He is successful in every deed (1 Sam

18:5, 7, 14-15, 27, 30) and has unshakable faith in the Lord (1 Sam 17:38-47; 2 Sam 7:18). He is a man sought out by the Lord, the one after the Lord’s own heart (1 Sam 13:14). He consults the Lord before every undertaking and takes courage from the Lord in moments of distress by seeking His counsel (1 Sam 23:1-6; 30:6-10; 2 Sam 2:1; 5:17-25) and is convinced of his own righteousness (2 Sam 22:21-24a).

He is noble and magnanimous (1 Sam 24 & 26; 2 Sam 1:11-12) and feels remorse and does not rejoice over the death of his archenemy (2 Sam 1:11-12). He is tolerant in the face of family rebellion and flees for his life (2 Sam 15:1-23). He is paternally concerned (2 Sam 18:28-32; 19:1, 5) and breaks down with inconsolable grief over the children (2 Sam 18:33-19:4). Moreover, he forgives those who curse and throw stones at him and his retinue (2 Sam 19:20-24). He listens to a woman (Abigail) and takes her counsel to heart and desists from carrying out his revengeful plan (1 Sam 25).

He is ‘protector’ of Judah (1 Sam 23, 25, 27), the shield of the mighty (2 Sam 1:21b; 22:3, 31, 36), the anointed of the Lord (1 Sam 24:26; 2 Sam 1; 1 Sam 16:13) and the chosen one (1 Sam 16:2). He refuses to raise his hand against the Lord’s anointed (1 Sam 24:2, 11; 26:9, 11, 16, 23). He is a powerful and great king (2 Sam 3:1; 8:1-18; 2 Sam 5:10) and destroyer of the enemies (2 Sam 22:38; 4:7, 8, 12; 16:9; 20:21; 1 Sam 17:46, 54, 57; 1 Sam 31:9). He is courageous (1 Sam 16:18). He is the head of the tribes of Israel (1 Sam 15:17) and the head of nations (2 Sam 22:44). He is kind even to the enemies (1 Sam 24:8-21; 26:7-13; 30:11-16; ch 25; 2 Sam 3:36; 2 Sam 9:7-8) and is loved and liked by all (1 Sam 18:13; 16:21; 18:3, 16, 22; 20:17; 2 Sam 12:24). He is benevolent (2 Sam 9:1) and administers justice and equity to all (2 Sam 8:15). He is the servant of God (2 Sam 3:18; 7:5, 8, 20, 21, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29) and expresses his own

servitude (2 Sam 8:10-11).

However the books of Samuel do not hide the shadows in David's life. His failure to be a true shepherd is exposed and he is rebuked (2 Sam 11:1). The idle king falls prey to the beauty of a bathing woman and commits adultery and then makes every effort to cover up his sin, even to the point of plotting to kill her husband (2 Sam 11:2-5). As a youngster, his ears perk up at the potential for fame and fortune (1 Sam 17:25-27) and he looks for a warrior's reward (1 Sam 17:26, 30). He seeks a spot within the royal family, first through an apparent feigned humility (1 Sam 18:18-19, 23), then through very aggressive and daring military prowess (1 Sam 18:27).

He becomes a proud warrior who acquires the spoils of war (1 Sam 17:54b), and who will cling to a gruesome trophy - the head of Goliath - even in later life (1 Sam 17:54a). He is arrogant (1 Sam 17:34-37a), boasts and seeks glory (2 Sam 8:13; 9:1, 3) and an impudent young man interested in seeing the fighting (1 Sam 17:28). His ruthlessness is exemplified when he does not win the hand of a woman who loves him, but rather, when he becomes the king's son-in law for purely political gain (1 Sam 18:26b). Likewise, he knowingly places the priest, Ahimelech in grave danger (1 Sam 21:2-10; 22:21). When the consequences of his actions are fulfilled, his 'repentance' is minimal. In contrast, he is more ostentatious in showing sorrow when the news of a death has greater political significance (2 Sam 1:11-27; 2:4b-7; 3:28-39; 4:9-12).

His opportunism is shown when he reverses his former decision and quickly renews his interest in Yahweh's ark, perhaps in his hope for a transferral of the blessing. (2 Sam 6: 12). He is still sensitive to the danger : instead of placing the ark in his own house the one Hiram helped him build

(2 Sam 5:11) he pitches a tent for it and offers sacrifices before it (2 Sam 6:17). He does not kill Saul and Absalom but actually looks forward to profiting from their death. He is distressed over Jonathan's death (2 Sam 26) but refrains from speaking directly of his own love for Jonathan. His tribute to the Lord may be seen as earning him the title of servant of the Lord (2 Sam 8:11-12) but his servitude could operate in a self-serving way as he himself appoints the high priests and makes his own sons as priests (2 sam 8:17-18).

His kindness to Me- ***His tribute to the Lord***
phibosheth (2 Sam 9:3) is ***may be seen as earning***
not out of his magnanim- ***him the title of servant of***
ity but due to his covenant ***the Lord, but his servitude***
with Jonathan, binding ***could operate in a self-***
himself to respect Jona- ***serving way as he himself***
than's request not "to cut ***appoints the high priests***
off your loyalty from ***and makes his own sons***
my house for ever" (1 ***as priests***
Sam 20:15). In spite of his

covenant with Jonathan (1 Sam 18:3-4) he has essentially placed Jonathan's son under house arrest (2 Sam 9). He showed kindness to Saul's house only after he allowed the gibeonites' sword to descend upon most of its occupants (2 Sam 21:1-9). He entices Abner (2 Sam 3:25-26) but does not prevent Joab to kill him. His continued disdain for Me- phibosheth is exemplified in his failure to bother with any form of cross-examination when Ziba brings charges against his master (2 Sam 16:1-4). He alludes to murder in the service of religion to rid himself of political rivals (2 Sam 21:1-7). He executes the majority of Saul's male heirs, after having vowed before Yahweh not to do this (1 Sam 24:22-23a). He becomes a passively failed father of Amnon and Tamar and

fails to correct them (2 Sam 13:1-20).

To summarize, David is a well-rounded character. The character emerging from his story is attractive and repulsive, noble and humane, good and evil, pleasing and sickening. His success is due to the divine patronage and favour. Only when he permits himself to be the recipient of Yahweh's favour, only when he permits his fate to rest in the hands of others, does the story present a fully positive view of him.

Endnotes

Endnotes

1. J. L. MCKENZIE, *The Old Testament Without Illusion* (Chicago 1979), 236.
2. S. TERRIEN, *The Elusive Presence: Toward a New Biblical Theology* (New York 1979), 282.
3. The expression "to consult the Lord" or "to inquire of the Lord" used about 42 times in the two books of Samuel, has the theological purpose of defining an individual's relationship with God, especially in the narratives describing the fall of Saul and the rise of David.
4. R. POLZIN, *Samuel and the Deuteronomist: A Literary Study of the Deuteronomistic History*, (Bloomington 1993) 62. Edelman notes the irony in that Goliath's head parallels the fate of Dagan's head in 1 Samuel 5. Cf. D.V. EDELMAN, *King Saul in the historiography of Judah* (JSOTS; Sheffield 1991) 133.
5. Lawton argues that the Merab-Michal device evokes the Leah-Rachel motif of Genesis 29. In this way, the author is able to highlight the fact that, unlike younger daughter Rachel, younger daughter Michal is not loved by her husband. cf. R.W. LAWTON, "1 Samuel 18: David, Merab and Michal", *CBQ* 51, (1989) 423-425.
6. R. POLZIN, *David and the Deuteronomist, A Literary Study of the Deuteronomistic History (Part Three: 2 Samuel)* (Bloomington 1993) 65.
7. J.P. FOKKELMAN, *Narrative Art and Poetry in the Books of Samuel. III. Throne and City* (11 Sam 2-8 and 21-24) (SSN 20; Assen 1990) 274.

Initiating a Dialogue with Nature: Lessons from Laudato Si'

Jeevan Neil Lobo

Masih Vidyapeeth, Agra

The very existence of the encyclical letter 'Laudato Si' is the causal effect of Man's unmanliness and ungodliness towards nature. Nature is the existential reality for both living and non-living; natural resources make a living for a being. The earth, by nature with motherly care sustains, governs and provides us required fruit for a living abundantly where man acts as the governor of nature. "The Lord God took the man and put him in the Garden of Eden to till it and keep it." (Gen; 2:15). The very words 'till it and keep it' has enormously changed over the time to 'use and throw' system in a way nobody is bothered about the mother earth at all. In this context, 'Laudato Si' unveils its vision for integrated ecology. The voice of Pontiff reaches to its highest peak to protect our common home without apathy, without negligence in order to rebuild broken relationship with nature.

It is good to know, etymologically; the term ecology has its origin in the Greek '*Oikos*' which means 'house' or 'home, the total environment in which living organisms exist. While the English term 'environment' is a derivation of the French 'environs' meaning thereby 'in circuit' or 'turning

around in'. That which makes ecology an environment is organism, its life style and the cycle of energy. Without this cycle of energy, there can't be adequate production and supply of resources in the environs.

Ever since the postmodern trend has put emphasis on science, technology and materialism, the height of man's respect and dignity has decreased; so much so that man has forgotten to respect nature. The advent of industrialization and capitalization has blocked wide view of human love and care for nature and has resulted in narrow relationship where 'self' stands first. Man with his technocratic mind, innovation and scienticism has given much emphasis on self and has neglected the rest of his surroundings. Things have so become objects to self that being, acts as a robot for him and others as mere objects rendering service. Man considers himself as homocentric being and tries to avoid any relationship that questions his self and dignity.

In ancient times human beings, who were natural beings depended on a healthy biosphere as other form of life. Their life was well constructed in

Man, who was supposed to relate with nature like a mother, sister or beloved, is in the process of discarding of the source of being like surplus waste in the courtyard.

the beautiful environment, they considered it as 'home' for their survival whereas now, it's the other way around. Man is a super being, the earth is a mere being, man is at the head level and earth is at the foot level, man makes a living by luxurious, deluxe and fascinating with artifacts while earth is crying for its survival, to live longer, to feed number of beings, to sustain many lives which man has yet to conceive

or grasp. What a pity! Man, who was supposed to relate with nature like a mother, sister or beloved, is in the process of discarding of the source of being like surplus waste in the courtyard. Man, who lived barefoot walking on the ground, wants marble stones and slabs for protection from nature. By doing so, he feels safe forgetting the walk on the green ground as healthy and medicinal.

In the words of Martin Heidegger, the phenomenologist philosopher, "Dasein's existential being in the world relates itself to the communal world of other Daseins. As being-with, Dasein is essentially for the sake of others. Then, Dasein is related to the environmental entities and communal entities." The world as the horizon enables humans to relate with environment communally. Dasein in his everydayness must care for three structural constituents; i.e. existentiality, facticity and fallen state. Care stands for the existential totality of Dasein's ontological structural whole. Dasein in his fallen state must recognize the facticity of his being in the world and that his existence is very phenomenal, the world is not to be served by him or to it but serve future generation. This facticity becomes a totality when Dasein understands that his existence is dependent on the environment.

Acknowledging the facticity of human nature with cause-effect and defects, is it not troubling one within or not at all? Well, there are troubled beings, untroubled beings, relaxed beings, beings that couldn't-be-bothered, care-giving beings when I especially quote 'Environment-Our Common Home'. The words of Pope Francis are right! We must have a dialogue of life for the new vision of humanity and integral ecology. Does it seem an easy task? Perhaps having a fair meeting with honourable leaders of nations seems interesting but how

far a change can be brought about? For instance, politicians may in themselves show their attitude of disrespect towards being and nature while giving oratorical-bombastic speeches.

Man with his crazy mentality has started to ignore every possible material. The products which are valuable today may not be tomorrow. Man does not want to see a change in him rather wants to see things being changed! Very strange! That man today does not want dust to settle on his feet and shoes to be settle on his feet touched at his feet but has no problem breathing the same air filled with dust particles.

In this case, can we consider our common home that the Pope is speaking about? The question is: “Who’s going to accept a change? Who’s ready to change? The Pope has beautifully spoken on Ecological Education and Spirituality. Education must transfer our very attitude, conviction, form of life and bringing about intelligible awareness. Walking in the light of reason, beings must continue to care for the creation of God. One must adopt ‘panentheism’ to praise the Lord for all creatures and to worship Him in union with them. One must discover the attitude of seeing God through natural means.

When one stands for collective goodness, we hope there wouldn't be any death due to malnutrition of babies, infants and children across the world. When being collaborates with nature by doing manual work, being in itself reciprocates with natural entity.

One must discover the attitude of seeing God through natural means.

Discovering such a presence may enable one to nurture ecological virtues. When ecological virtues enabled in being, there would drastically be a sense of deep communion with the rest of nature. One may move forward with compassion

and concern. When this sense of deep communion is rooted, one enters into the realm of universal communion where there will be no place for indifference, cruelty and hatred towards being and nature on a communal level. If everything is related, united and connected, we’ll be sharers and bearers of our mother earth; not only that, it is the responsibility of sharers to be loyal and faithful. The needs must be fulfilled by each and every social being without distinction of caste and creed, privileged and unprivileged, and haves and have-nots. Since every being is a dignified being, man in his earthly abode must regard each being instead of causing unnecessary separation and isolation.

Therefore, man must forgo the greed of his self in order to have pluralism, collective goodness and harmony in humanity and nature. When one stands for collective goodness, we hope there wouldn’t be any death due to malnutrition of babies, infants and children across the world. When being collaborates with nature by doing manual work, being in itself reciprocates with natural entity. By way of personal work, being experiences the essence of nature, the dynamism of nature and the intrinsic value of nature which may imbue one’s relationship with the world with healthy sobriety.

Since man has become a creative designer, he requires to develop interrelationship between living space and human behaviour, especially while building mansions for loved ones, building for married ones and palaces for newly-wedded couples. By being aware, let one not reduce the beauty of nature rather increase its freshness, calm, serenity and a sense of belonging wherever a being makes a home in the common home. Therefore, one must accept to learn about self, the quality of life and to respect other beings and stand

for the common good of everyone on earth.

The Pope also insists on transparency in the decision-making. The values of ecology must be lifted up while dealing with projects that threaten loss of environment and its destruction. There needs to be a moderate level of production and cut down of over – production and corruption of nature. The global development needs to be humanly - humane, rational, ethical, and eco- progressive and friendly. Hence, stressing on eco – spirituality, the institutions should become responsible models for ecological growth. The Christians in church, seminarians and formation houses must meet God in each and every atom of His beautiful creation. Students, seminarians and formees are to be trained to protect God’s awesome work. The internal expressions of prayer, sermons, novenas, etc., are to be explicitly expressed in works towards ecological growth. Priests, religious must be more concerned on ecological needs as they preach the Gospel of Word. The Gospel must be the enhanced tool in hands of missionaries to till the land to bear fruit and rejuvenate the spirit of ecology, especially in the minds of people. When this takes place, certainly there will be renewal in humanity.

Well, having collected various means of transformative steps set by Pontiff, it is aptly right to begin somewhere at someplace phenomenally where life originates. Albeit, biologically life begins its formation at the womb, but mental and physical formation takes place outside the womb. The education which posits values, deeds and character shapes a living; above all, being is intrinsically a being of innate qualities especially love. According to Varghese Kottoor CMI, a scholar in “Inner Smile” says “Love is a divine energy, an energy that instills life, spreads love and light.

When a person holds an inner smile the energy of love is created and radiated in and around atmosphere.” Therefore, it is love amongst all qualities broods in a small family, grows in society, spreads in community, prospers in the nation; which should be the asset of an eco-friendly and family-spirited nature.

Today, the human brain is formed in such a way; that one fails to become one with nature and finds

“Love is a divine energy, an energy that instills life, spreads love and light.”

it hard to relate with nature.

It is, therefore, the priority of any family to teach children -values, ethics of nature, love-care towards beings and nature and building healthy relationship with the environment. When a family does eco-friendly acts , for sure it cannot be paraded before neighbors; can be a workable matter of practice and interest. Suppose, hundreds of families do the same, will there not be a place for better ecology? Of course, it’s possible, unless and until one does have a self-actualizing phenomenon and realization. “Self-actualization occurs only when the self is directed outward from itself to the world of things and persons.” Thus we attain self-actualization not by collecting and adding things to ourselves but by being genuine to the basic outward dynamism in us. Realization takes place when an object is given input by the object of experience. Thus these two elements are necessary diet for mind activity. Because, the materialistic world has made man – a mere material object forgotten to imbibe qualities that makes man-man. With the idea of money, power and sex which govern world, man still considers, they are the source and summit of everything. The concept of values and God are far from the mind of human beings and has vanished from

the human dictionary!

In this situation, man must first become human and to be human, man must be infused with an attitude of self-actualization and realization that his deeds were misdeeds. In other words, his misdeeds have become his deeds. The man who considered others and earth as an object must now necessarily needs to change his or her views to subject-subject ideology. When a being looks at other beings with the attitude of subject–subject relation and not mere object, a restoration of attitude in mind and body may take place. Victor Frankl says, “In love, the beloved is comprehended in every essence, as the unique and singular being that he is; he is comprehended as a “thou”, and, as such, is taken into the self.” When a person loves without seeking any gain it becomes the formation of true love relationship. Because, love is not deserved, it is unmerited and is simply grace. When love is able to see through the needle of an eye, it surely will be able to touch the core of others with same values that a lovable being holds. When love is essentially formed in the human heart with rationale, it spreads with others just like the fragrance of a flower. When a being is able to build relationships with other beings, automatically the relationship builds up with nature. Above all, the relationship is divinely connected to the divinity of Being. That is; love is shared in a triangular way between human – nature, nature – God and God – human. How beautiful would this have been if this could have been established!

Therefore, every being has the inner potential to love, love that composes, actualizes, moulds, and transforms human limitations and boundaries of sense knowledge. When one loves, one affirms the very values for which one is striving

with his whole humanity: the fullness of knowledge, of love and of communion. When one loves, one testifies to one’s own identity and one’s own demand to transcend oneself and to give oneself. Here opens up the root source of human dignity and uniqueness in living a human life that stands for not self alone but for others. Though man, overtime has had the idea of being ‘crown of creation’ powering over nature; it is required of him to bend down and care for nature that

has been left derelict and totally uncared for. Today, man must pass over from the anthropocentric perspective to the biocentric perspective. The *When one loves, one testifies to one’s own identity and one’s own demand to transcend oneself and to give oneself.*

environment needs an equal right to be protected, related and cultivated not for humans alone but for other living beings too.

In the 20th century, preservationists such as John Muir held that “the intrinsic value of natural areas, particularly wilderness areas, creates responsibilities for humanity.” The action of being towards nature ought to be of high moral standard, good and respectful. Man must find himself an inherent worth of living if his living needs to be a better living. When inherent worth strikes man, subsequently man will find inherent worth in all living beings. He would certainly promote and protect. Will these simple few acts suffice? Necessarily not! These above mentioned strategies are personal, can be limited to family, neighborhood, etc. There are others who can approach the system in society. For instance; being climate friendly, proposing climate friendly actions, environmental talks, awareness in localities, being

climate conscious, awareness on recycling, reusing, avoiding deforestation, minimum packaging, installing water-tanks to collect rain water for garden, field, using solar panels for electricity, trying to keep tidy the surroundings with go-green policy, watering plants at sunset rather than the heat of the day, sapling-plantation, providing funds for ecological organizations, using compost heap or wormery as they recycle organic waste including food and produce excellent compost, using public transport, other than personal vehicle are other means of pro-friendly action one can do, promote such activities in schools, colleges, church, blogs, society, medias, etc.

Apart from these, man must initiate an ongoing dialogue with nature. There must be harmony with nature with respect and love by availing of the potentialities of nature and that of humankind for the smooth progress and development of both man and nature. Man must take the example of St. Francis Assisi, the par excellence of care for the vulnerable and of an integral ecology, who lived out joyfully, authentically speaking, with natural entities, calling them ‘sisters and brothers.’ one needs to open our the heart towards nature to transcend the empirical subjects of text-books and go beyond to understand the beautiful creation of God.

Man, by all his misdeeds knowingly and unknowingly, has damaged ecology which needs restoration by us humans. Man, with all his love and will-power, requires to change his behavior and attitude to experience the real warmth of nature. Alongside, the dialogue with conservationists, lovers of ecology, leaders, are to be infused somehow with fire for protection of the environment if our “common home” is to be saved! Thus, life cannot be life without parts. It should

consist of atoms. Similarly, ecology can’t be an integrated ecology without the two hands of man, will of being, lovely care of being; due respect for nature and empathy are a must. Man can’t stand alone without something and that “without something” is nothing but nature.

Finally, the divine and human aspirations of Pope Francis to establish the Kingdom of God with rigorous and zealous mission; alongside ardent support, co-operation and collaboration of all humanity will be appreciated as the first innovative step to restore creative environment. Nonetheless, the Kingdom of God will be restored if human beings progressively work towards the common aim: “To save our Common Home.” Thus, “*Laudato Si, mi’ Signore*” – Praise be to you, my Lord” of Pope Francis will be fulfilled at the right time by Divine intervention in human reality.

Endnotes

1. Throughout this article the term ‘man’ is used to include :women’ also.
2. Pope Francis, *Encyclical Letter Laudato Si’* (Trivandrum: CIPH, 2015), 143.
3. Varghese Kottoor, “The Power of Inner Smile” (Paper presented at the Students Mission League of the Institute of Masih Vidyapeeth, Agra, September 22, 2017).
4. John Kavanaugh, *Human Realization: An Introduction to the Philosophy of Man* (New York: Corpus Books, 1971), 146.
5. Viktor Frankl, *Man’s Search for Meaning: An Introduction to Logo therapy* (New Delhi: Simon and Schuster, 1989), 180.
6. John Muir, “Nature Conservationists”, in *Encyclopedia Britannica*, 8th ed.
7. Pope Francis, *Encyclical Letter Laudato Si’* (Trivandrum: CIPH, 2015), 7.

Caring for One Another: *Laudato Si'* and Harmonious Development

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The fetters of imperialism and colonization are broken forever and have faded into the pages of history. Yet the question arises deep down in our hearts, are we free to enjoy the world around us or does it still threaten us? While the world is moving towards progress with exhilarating speed, humans have marched to the fringes of the earth, unaware that they may lose the grip any time. Great will be that fall! At this juncture we could hear voices that whisper, “The world stands in need of liberation, my Lord, it still has to learn to love.” Have the freedom and progress we have acquired escaped from our hands? *Laudato Si* “praise be to you” the encyclical of Pope Francis places before us certain challenges to get back the grip that we have lost and fix our feet on the ground in congruence with the nature around us.

Pope Francis’ encyclical on ecological issues was not so palatable to all. The US Republican candidate, Rick Santorum, pointed out that, “We probably are better off, leaving science to scientists and focusing on what we are really good at – theology and morality”. Why did Pope Francis officially teach about ecological issues and insist on caring for the “common home”, instead of concentrating on matters concerning faith and morals? No doubt we are in a crisis,

treading towards irreparable havoc, unless we save the earth. It is a reality beyond religion and science, a reality which is ready to consume us any time.

This essay embodies a new vision of humanity envisioned in the light of *Laudato Si'* and mentions certain practical tips to shoulder the responsibility in building a better world for the next generation. However, we deal with a few crucial environmental issues of the 21st Century which are elaborately discussed in the encyclical, because awareness is the initial step towards any desired change. Environment is an umbrella term which includes both society and nature. Hence, social and ecological problems are intertwined and this essay focuses from this angle.

1. Alarming Terrorist Attacks

Human beings are being massacred in the name of religion, language, selfish motives, hatred and war. ISIS had orchestrated more than hundred terrorist attacks by now and attacks on Syria are a nightmare for us. India has witnessed a number of terrorist attacks in the recent past. Indian Churches and other minorities are also facing a type of terrorist attack behind the garb of Hindutva ideology.

Our attitude towards nature around us is also rather violent. A kind of eco-terrorism is being operated day by day towards our Mother Earth, by our irresponsible use and abuse of the products of nature. The violence present in our hearts, as her lords and masters, plunder her, forgetting our bodies, are made up of her elements (LS 2). Mercilessly we chop trees to make her barren, rape her relentlessly through undue mining and crush her womb. Deforestation and desertification for our comforts and to establish our kingdom is a terrorist attack we inflict on our Mother Earth.

We choke her with polluted air, threaten her with noise. Pollution caused by transport, industry, farms and smoke from fuels used in cooking or heating are hazards to the eco-system (LS 20). In the name of technology, progress and amassing wealth, we are all partners in this act of terrorism. Who will fight against this and bring justice to Mother Earth?

2. Voiceless Refugees

“A refugee is someone who has been forcibly displaced because of war, persecution ethnic violence or human rights violation.” We are aware of the Rohingyas of Myanmar who had to flee away from their country. The war stricken eastern countries have sent out millions as migrants. Among the 66 million displaced persons in the world, almost 23 million are from Syria, Afghanistan and South Sudan. They are the vulnerable people of the society and their children have lost their childhood forever. To be a refugee is terrible! Are only human beings made refugees?

A large number of animals and birds are migrating to other places due to climate changes or in search of food. Since forests and woodlands are plundered for our economy, commerce, production and comforts, animals and plants have lost their habitats. Birds and insects disappear due to ergotoxines used for agriculture. We destroy innumerable variety of microorganisms which are required to maintain the equilibrium of the ecosystem (LS 34). “Each year sees the disappearance of thousands of plant and animal species which we will never know, which our children will never see, because they have been lost forever. The great majority become extinct for reasons related to human activity” (LS 33).

3. Degradation of Value System

We live in a world of constant change which *Laudato Si* phrases as ‘rapidification’. This constant change is not geared to common good and becomes a source of anxiety rather than sustainable human development (LS 18). In the name of change, we are slowly losing the ground of our value system. Interconnectedness and interdependence have given way for individualism and selfishness. ‘Might is right’ is our slogan and we fail to respect life and others. *Laudato Si* elaborates a few anti-cultural values that we are treading towards which in turn create a devastating climate change (LS 23-26).

a. Throw Away Culture

Our throw away culture reduces things to rubbish and fails to reuse and recycle them. Pope Francis states, that “The earth, our home, is beginning to look more and more like an immense pile of filth” (LS 21-22).

b. Culture of Corruption

In recent years values of honesty and truthfulness have been downgraded. Corruption is the ruling principle. Our activities have corrupted the planet earth too. The satellite pictures paint earth as a blue planet covered with water. Major corruption and contamination are done against the blue blanket of the earth. The Papal document *Laudato Si* speaks vehemently against water issues. The availability of fresh drinking water is diminishing. The quality of water available to the poor is unsafe resulting in many deaths (LS 28-29).

c. Culture of Indifference

In this digital world we entertain an attitude of indifference. We are blind to the sufferings of fellow humans as well

as to the natural environment. Most of the environmental attacks gravely affect the poorest of the society. The encyclical challenges all “to hear both the cry of the earth and the cry of the poor.” (LS 49). Having created a bird’s eye view of the present scenario of our environment in the light of *Laudato Si* let us sketch ‘a new vision of humanity.’

4. A New Vision of Humanity

A native American proverb says, “We have not inherited the earth from our ancestors, we have borrowed it from our children.” Hence, we have to return it to them intact. Pope Francis asks us in *Laudato Si*, “What kind of world do we want to leave to those who come after us, to children who are now growing up?” (LS160).

a. Peaceful and Harmonious Environment

Peace was the parting gift Jesus imparted to His disciples (John 20:19). Suicidal cases, family breakdown, health hazards, emotional imbalances, anxiety, stress, intolerance, loneliness and hopelessness are on high ranking level than in the past. The gigantic task that lies before us is to establish peace with oneself, others and nature. In *Laudato Si* Pope Francis says peace does not mean absence of sufferings or war rather, “inner peace is closely related to care for ecology and for the common good” (LS 225). There is an urgent need to slow down our rat race to amass wealth and comfort, to experience the gentleness of the cool breeze, the purity of clean water and its rhythmic flow, the tranquilizing effect of greenery which fill our minds with lasting peace.

Peace overflows from within like a river to others. This is the sacred hour to join hands together to break the walls of hatred, violence, war, religious fanaticism and terrorism. We

have wounded fellow humans as well as Mother Earth. It is our obligation to bind up the wounds caused to Mother Earth and to others. Let us dream a new world for our children, “where people have food and houses and enjoyable work, where animals and plants and human beings live together on earth in harmony, where none shall hurt and destroy”. This was God’s vision we read in the book of Isaiah: “For I am about to create a new heaven and a new earth; ...no more shall the sound of weeping be heard in it or the cry of the distress...” (Is 65:17-25).

b. Interdependent and Interconnected Environment

The universe in which we live is one, interrelated yet diverse and complex. It is an indivisible reality. A greater awareness of interdependence will eradicate a number of ecological abuses and exploitation (LS 265). We have evolved together with the cosmos and are entirely dependent on certain conditions of the earth such as water, air, food, climate, land etc. In fact, we came into existence much later. In the Bible we read “The earth is the Lord’s and all that is in it, the world, and those who live in it” (Ps 24:1). The early Christian anthropology has wrongly interpreted human relationship with world and they considered themselves as masters of all. Instead of dominating, we need to be responsible stewards. Hence, we need to move from anthropocentrism to interconnectedness (LS 115-119).

However, human degradation and nature degradation are two sides of the same coin. Poverty is an ecological problem as much as violation of biodiversity of nature. Thus interconnectedness and interdependence must encourage us to raise the standard of living of our poor sisters and brothers. *Laudato Si* also summons us to protect the human embryo – the

most vulnerable beings (LS 120). Thus, *Laudato Si* invites the whole of humanity to be harbingers of a culture of life.

c. A Clean Environment

The greatest gift we give to the next generation might be a clean environment. We have already seen how our environment looks like a pile of filth through human activities. Let our rivers flow clean, free of sewage and other industrial waste, design plastic-free surroundings. The Modi Government has taken up the project of ‘Swachh Bharath’ to ensure cleanliness. We are in crisis not because we lack projects rather serious implementation of it. In our country primarily, we need to get rid of our constant habit of throwing things haphazardly or littering, spitting and urinating anywhere. Clean environment requires fresh air. Reduction of green gas effect and other causes of global warming have to be tackled, otherwise our children will be strangled to death. Pure water, fresh air and a noise free environment will make the next generation healthy and vibrant.

d. Eco-Just Environment

“The human environment and the natural environment deteriorate together; we cannot adequately combat environmental degradation unless we attend to causes related to human and social degradation” (LS 48). We have become so insensitive to the weaker sections of society and push them mercilessly to the periphery. While we try to show justice to nature let us also embrace the least, last and lost in the society. To elicit a few examples, during Modi’s regime a coal-fired power plant ‘Mundra Ultra Mega Power Project’ was built at Mundra in Gujarat. It destroyed the environment that had sustained local fishing and business for generations. The Global Hunger Index ranked India 97th among 118 countries.

The studies by World Food Programme show that one person in eight goes hungry each night though we have sufficient food to feed the entire 7 billion people. Are we living in a just society? Eco- Justice requires of us to respect the intrinsic worth of earth and all its components. Even, if we do not see a purpose for their existence, the Creator has a purpose and has endowed them with an intrinsic value.

e. Sustainably Developing Environment

Brundtland Commission defines, “Sustainable development is, development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs”. The present efforts to growth are quick, overdrawn from the natural resources and without the vision of future generations. In fact, we borrow environmental capital from the future generation without the consciousness of repaying it back. However, sustainable development not only takes account of the future but also embraces all while protecting nature. It is not a shallow economic progress that we envision for the future, rather a wholesome development which sustains both social and ecological environment.

The behaviour of those who constantly consume and destroy is unsustainable which deprives some others of living a life worthy of their human dignity. This has given rise to disparity among nations. The principle of the maximization of profits, frequently isolated from other considerations is a wrong concept of economy. In case of poverty and environmental degradation both politics and the economy tend to blame each other. While one group tries to stabilize the financial gain, the other establishes the power and the weaker sections of the society pay the price. Today we require a politics which is far sighted and capable of a new, integral

and interdisciplinary approach to handle the different aspects of the crisis, able to work in hand with the economy (LS 193-198). Thus, we may present to the future a sustainably developing environment to burn their torch.

f. Eco- Spiritual Environment

Humans are psycho-spiritual-social-rational beings. Therefore, every person has an aspiration to be in communion with the divine. In order to create an eco-spiritual environment, we need to undergo an “ecological conversion”, which enables us to be more passionately engaged in the protection of the world.

Living our vocation to be protectors of God’s handiwork is an essential virtue. Quoting the example of Saint Francis of Assisi, from whose canticle Pope Francis borrowed the title of the book itself, attempts to unravel the spiritual depth we can gain from nature. Healthy relationship with creation enabled the conversion of Saint Francis of Assisi and filled his heart with tenderness. The encyclical asks us, to recognize the world as God’s loving gift, with gratitude and gratuitousness. Universal communion, dialogue and an ecological conversion can inspire us to greater creativity and enthusiasm in resolving the world’s problems. *Laudato Si* also suggests a number of practical tips to enhance our spirituality namely, be happy with little, return to simplicity that allows us to stop and appreciate the small things, be grateful for the opportunities life affords us, be spiritually detached from what we possess and not to succumb to sadness for what we lack (LS 216-226).

Above all, it teaches us that eco-spirituality is part of the spiritual quest of every religion which would bring greater communion among people of different religions. In real-

ity every religion has a close association with nature. The second chapter of the book clearly depicts how Christianity is closely associated with nature and places before us the grave responsibility to save nature. Hence creating a school of eco-spirituality in union with various religions will definitely help the next generation to live as children of God and to experience Him significantly in nature.

Having spelt out our vision as contributed by *Laudato Si*, let us draw up a concrete action plan for a new life style.

5. A New Life Style

- Make a shift from consumerist life style and throw away culture. Avoid wasting food items. Segregate wet and dry waste at homes and institutes. Cultivate personal vegetable garden and buy local products.
- Clean up after our use: Let “reuse, recycle and reduce” be our motto. Use water sparingly. In our schools and other institutes, recycle the water we use in wash rooms and reuse it. Encourage rain harvesting and adopt agricultural crops based on seasons. Recycle the used paper and use it sparingly.
- Conserve energy: Our travel can be by walk or bicycles for short distances and avoid the luxury of travelling in private vehicles often. Reduce the use of decorative lights and even number of lights in a room and switch off immediately after our use than being careless.
- Ecological education: Introduce protection of environment as a practical subject in seminaries and religious institutes, especially in our schools. Make Interreligious gatherings and political forum for discussions on this theme.

Conclusion

The encyclical *Laudato Si'* is not a mere source of information, rather a call to conversion, to take a 'U' turn to 'the common home' – to nurture nature, to accept our identity as one of the interdependent creatures. Although it elaborates on the ecological crisis, the thrust is on conversion at all levels of life - personal, business, employment and the choices that we make to be proactive "to hear the cry of the earth and the cry of the poor" (LS 49). It enormously contributes to renewing and refashioning the broken planet for future generations as the Creator has designed it. The encyclical summons us to have a global consensus to adapt new models to 'care for the common home'. Let my country, the world at large, arise into that freedom where humanity and nature travel in the same vehicle, with same speed, caring for one another.

Notes

1. Jacob Naluparayil, "Francis and Environment", *Smart Companion*, Vol.6, No.6, (June 2015), 3.
2. Joe Mannath, "Refugees", *The New Leader*, Vol. 130, No.23, (December 2017), 7.
3. Ibid. 7.
4. "Thousand Words", *Jivan*, (December 2017- January 2018), 15.
5. Sallie Mcfague, *A New Climate for Theology*, (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2008), 144.
6. Mohan Dass, "Promoting an Eco-Just Humanity: An Interfaith Exploration", *Ishvani Documentation and Mission*, Vol. 33, No.3, (September-December 2015), 243-274.
7. Cedric Prakash, "Environment Matters", *Smart Companion* Vol.6, No.6, (January 2015), 30-31.
8. Joyce Sebastian, "Hunger Games: A Different Kind", *Indian Currents*, Vol. XXVIII, No. 43 (October 2016), 32-35.
9. Felix Wilfred, "Eco-Justice: Expanding the Horizons for a Common Future", *Jeevadhara*, Vol. XL, No. 235, (January 2010), 5-17.
10. Joseph Peruma, *The Motherly Earth*, (Bangalore: Claretian Publications, 2002), 177.

A New Vision of Humanity: Contribution of *Laudato Si'*

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Darśana: Introduction

Bṛhadaraṇyaka Upaniṣad has a beautiful story of Prajapati (Creator Lord) and his offspring (gods, men, and demons) practicing the vow of brahmacārins. When the offspring asked the Lord to instruct them, he uttered "da". The Lord speaks to us in "da's"; like the heavenly thunder 'da', 'da', 'da' I will be using this analogy to explicate the new vision of the Pontiff in a series of da's, one leading to the other, beginning with the first 'da' Darśana (glimpses in Sanskrit).

1. Dúrdṛṣṭi: Vision, Foresight (Sanskrit)

Dúrdṛṣṭi is our second 'da'. The mighty green wave has swept the Vatican up leaving it green in her social and ecclesial endeavours. Sooner or later it had to come about, as the famous dictum goes 'the mills of Rome grind you slowly but they grind you for sure'. The Church too has plunged into the Greens, which made the scientific community grin at the Vatican, saying "*Laudato Si', mi' Signore et Laudato Si', mi' Vatican*" (Praise be to You, my Lord, and praise be to you, My Vatican).

Does Humanity have a vision? Of course, it does. For ages humanitarian visions in the West were the extensions of religious beliefs and Greco-Roman philosophies, same is true

with the East except for the fact that there was no distinction between the religion and the philosophies. Scientific and philosophical advances have, time and again, questioned these age-old visions for humanity. Not that the visions of bygone era were faulty, they were relevant then. For our troubled times they just need to be corrected, upgraded and revised. In other words, we need a New Vision of Humanity. Visions are dynamic, they are never static; they evolve as the time passes by. Historical development of this vision of Humanity could be comprehended and traced through the development of 'human rights', because the world need to "speak of *being* over that of *being useful*" (LS 69).

Human Rights: Humans are the precious gifts of Judaeo-Christian and Greco-Roman traditions. In a world of '*unequals*', human rights restore the dignity of the poor and the powerless. Human rights have developed in five stages. At the very first stage political and civil rights were given to select citizens, then come the economic and social rights. The third stage is marked with the cultural, ethnic and, communitarian rights. The devastating world wars shuddered humanity and enlightened people about the worth of 'life', so, the fourth stage is marked with '*right to life*'. The recent addition to the human rights family is the '*right to environment*'. The Pontiff in his encyclical writes about the environmental crises and calls for a radical change, ecological conversion. The contribution of *Laudato Si*' towards a new vision of humanity is "*Ecological-Social-Justice*".

Cenozoic Age to Ecozoic Age: The cultural historian Thomas Berry claims that "we are at the end of Cenozoic age, the era of geological history that began some 65 million years ago and are moving into the Ecozoic age". The

Ecozoic age envisioned by Berry would be an era of mutually enhancing *human-earth* relationships. The *human-earth* relationship calls for a revolution in our understanding of our existence. We get to see the same flavour in the Papal encyclical, methodically elaborating and driving the point home of a new vision of Humanity. It has a starting point in joining St Francis of Assisi in calling the Earth, Sister/Mother earth.

2. Demeter: Mother Earth/Sister Earth, Eco-Feminism?

The third '*da*', '*Demeter*' is a Greek goddess of harvest, agriculture, and the life cycle. Even *Zeus* had to bow down to her. When she was angry about her daughter's abduction, everything came to standstill. Symbolically she sustains the life on earth.

For the first time in the history of the Catholic Church, a Pontiff has called the earth *Sister/Mother Earth*; something unheard of in Christian spheres. Be that as it may, the feminine terminology to address the earth and the environmental issues will be ground-breaking when it comes to changing the western-world view, that has done irreparable damage to the common home.

The Pontiff quotes **the canticle of St Francis** "Praise be to you, my Lord, through our Sister, Mother Earth, who sustains and governs us, and who produces various fruit with coloured flowers and herbs", and calls the earth, *Sister and Mother*. "This sister now cries out to us because of the harm we have inflicted on her by our irresponsible use and abuse of the goods with which God has endowed her" (LS 2). The mandate in the Genesis '*to have dominion*' over the earth had distorted the Judaeo-Christian worldview, it is St Francis who "healed that rupture" (LS 66) through the universal

reconciliation with every creature by calling the creatures of the world sisters and brothers.

Why are these feminine attributions so important?

Because they embody profound meaning and significance for the world that is in need of healing. Seeing environmental crises in general and climate change in particular with feminine eyes, there is a shift in Church's attitude from one that of *Conquistador to Caring*; for women are better endowed with caring faculties. Ursula King thinks that "Women's respect for life and their potential for motherhood give them a special sensitivity to ecological and environmental issues, and suggest the possibility of a special female contribution in this area". Women share with nature the ability and the experience of bringing forth and sustaining life. The acute sense of the patriarchal hegemony and exploitation of this women-nature bond necessitates a new vision. The new liberative vision considers women-nature not as 'the Other', nor 'the Alienated' but that which completes, the complementary. We cannot see nature devoid of feminine energy, the feminine dimension is an important dimension to understand the ecological reality. Everything is interconnected, so is the femininity with nature.

3. Dharma: Theory of Everything

Dharma (the fourth 'da') is the principle that keeps the cosmic order (ṛta) intact, a little ruffle in the practice of dharma (towards nature, neighbour) can cause havoc. The Theory of Everything is all that unifies the big and the small, a single theory that explains everything and links all physical aspects together. Finding a theory of everything is one of the major unsolved problems in physics. Stephen Hawking called it "Knowing the Mind of God", to know how things

are connected is to know the mind of God. The Chaos Theory speaks of the "Butterfly Effect"; a flap of a butterfly in Pune can cause a cyclone in Pentagon. Which goes to say that everything is intricately connected and linked. In Christian tradition we speak of one incarnation, that is of Jesus; but in Vedic tradition God incarnates Himself in various forms of nature. Here, God is the common thread that weaves and build the ecology, the earth: our common home. *Laudato Si'* is that theory today which says everything is connected. "Everything that has happened in the whole course of the universe is present in each one of us, just like every atom is in contact with and affects every other atom of the universe." Genuine care for our own lives and our relationships with nature is inseparable from fraternity, justice and faithfulness to others. Everything is interconnected : progress, degradation of environment, scientific advances, economy, and social justice.

The ancient scriptures of the East tell us that there is a covenant relation between nature and humanity. It is said and believed in India that when a woman is pregnant, no tree is cut in the village or in the vicinity to mark the respect for life. They deeply believe that everything is connected. If this was true then in India, we would never face any environmental crises; but in reality, we do have serious problems. This tells us that somewhere the common good is sacrificed over the personal/individual good. Thus, they end-up messing with the integrity and cosmic-equilibrium that exist in the universe. When we see the common thread, which unites all different expressions of human culture and heritage, we have a full sense of human welfare. It also entails a loving awareness that we are not disconnected from the rest of creatures, but joined in a *dharma* of splendid universal communion.

Unjust development has disrupted *dharmic* principle causing *adharma*. So we need to strive towards the progress of all.

4. Development and Dike: Progress and Justice (*Sabka Saath Sabka Vikaas*)

Ecological Conversion: *Development* and *Dike* (Justice in Greek) are taken together, they are the fifth and the sixth “**da’s**”. In the new vision of humanity, the *development* and *dike* go together. Where there is justice there is development. *Sabka Saath Sabka Vikaas*’ (Collective efforts, inclusive growth) captured Indians and Modi rose to power in 2014. Heavily loaded slogan but its actualisation is far from reality in the BJP led government of India. The Pontiff, in 2015, also called for collective efforts from both the rich and the poor to strive towards a sustainable/integral development (*Sandhāarit Vikas*, and not just *Vikaas*). The social analysis tells us that 80% of the world resources are consumed by the developed nations who amount to just the 20% of the world population. Developed nations have developed at the expense of the poor, now that there are crises from the fact that these nations want everybody to plunge into the task of saving the planet. Environmental crisis is a by-product of the exclusive non-sustainable development of the powerful (nations). There is a profound relation between the poor and the fragility of the planet. The more fragile the planet more vulnerable are the poor to natural calamities. The poor are always caught off guard with meagre means to cope with the ecological crises. This is where the ‘*ecological debt*’ exist that the rich owe to the poor. The gravest effects of all attacks on the environment are suffered by the poorest. This calls for a deeper reflection to save the planet earth from man-made disasters; the ecological crisis is also a summons

to profound interior conversion, an ecological conversion.

Environmental Social Justice (*Dike*): For ages the poor were excluded from the so called ‘economic growth’, ‘development’, ‘scientific advances’, that have turned out to be detrimental to the environment. The poor are poor because they are lazy, the famous argument of the rich against the poor. Does the poor, even, have the opportunities to work hard, come up in life? Even if they do, their labour has no claim over the profit. It is the structure that helps the rich become richer; because it is designed by the rich. The unjust system vehemently leads to social injustice. The social injustice towards the poor has its repercussions on the environment. The environmental crises have ripped the poor apart from the little that they had; nature can be cruel to the poor. The ‘*throwaway culture of the rich*’ abuses the natural resources and deprives the poor of their resources; the resources of the earth belong to the poor too. This is the *ecological debt* that the rich owe to the poor. The day the rich realize this debt and start paying the poor what belongs to them, there will be environmental social justice; justice done to the poor is justice done to the environment.

We think that we are making progress, but our progress is like that of the *deer* in the desert, who

The ‘throwaway culture of the rich’ abuses the natural resources and deprives the poor of their resources; the resources of the earth belong to the poor too.

chases after a mirage. The poor *deer* runs deep into the desert until it can go no further, led on by its burning thirst, trapped in its blindness and misjudgement, it eventually lies down to die in the wilderness. The further we progress along this path, the deeper our disillusionment becomes. If present trends

continue, this century may well witness extraordinary climate change and an unprecedented destruction of ecosystems, with serious consequences for all of us (LS 24). Our technological progress is to be re-looked at. How could anyone, even, claim to be building a better future without thinking of the environmental crisis and the sufferings of the excluded? Pope Francis' encyclical has been "promoting what some perceive to be new understandings- such as of progress being integral to ecological concerns" and the "call to establish a dialogue involving all of Humanity." Therefore, 'vikaas' can never be 'vikaas' if it is not 'sabka vikaas', environment included.

5. Dialogue: An Essential Element of Coexistence

The seventh 'da' is the *dialogue*, the fullness of "da's". For our troubled and tumultuous times when the world politics is governed by the right-wing forces, it is all the more difficult to shift the focus of the people in power to environmental issues which are not on their priority list. Structuro-attitudinal change is required for a green revolution and make the earth, a heaven again. Dialogue will make it possible to work for the common good of our common home. It's a must for co-existence of humans and nature. Nature may flourish without humans but humans need nature; it is a *sine qua non*. It is in best interest of humanity to take care of environment, that sustains life here on earth. Dialogue between:

1. **Nature and Humans:** Hypothetically humans need to strike a dialogue with nature and know what significant role it plays in human existence.
2. **Nations:** Dialoguing to bring all the nations to combat environmental crises, and making it mandatory for the developed nations to have stringent policies against violators. The poor countries also need to

caution people to curb pollution; because they still use the age-old methods/machineries in the industries.

3. **Science and Religion:** Science and Religions do not have the same objective, here one is not opposite to the other, but when they are brought together science can rip religion of its superstitions and religion can rip science of idolatry.
4. **Disciplines (Interdisciplinary):** dialoguing with disciplines like, philosophy, sociology, psychology, Science and technology etc can shed light on the gravity of the crises. This approach nearly exhausts the multiple dimensions of the problem and helps us to come up with an integral response.
5. **Humans:** Humans are yet to know the importance of the ecological balance. Dialoguing and carefronting the other in matters of ecology is essential; for it concerns the entire planet.

Dialogue has the power of reconciliation, reconciliation with the other, with the excluded, with the environment, with the ecology and with the creation. The Pontiff knows it very well that ecological concern, detached from a social justice perspective would be far away from the reality and sound elitist. So, the Pope makes the new vision down-to-earth and achievable.

6. Conclusion: Re-interpreting our Destiny

The eighth 'da' *destiny* is the summary of the seven da's; the observance of the first seven da's decide our planet's destiny. Theological rupture needs immediate attention of humans before it is too late. The Pontiff is inviting the global

community to respond collectively to the gravest of the grave problem that haunts us today. The immediacy with which humans need to respond to the crises is seen in the secular and undogmatic tone of the encyclical in appealing to world populace. Pope uses the word ‘today’ 29 times which stresses the urgency with which we need to act now.

We have umpteen number of scientific studies done on the subject of environmental crises to go to the basis of the problem. What lies down under was looked and searched before, but from the centre taking a popular world-view. The Church is the last to speak about the environmental issues. There are scholars who have spoken about this but in vain. Nobody is serious about it. The Pontiff re-interprets them from ‘below’— a bottom-up approach, from the periphery, from the perspective of the poor, from the perspective of women, and for us in India from the perspective of the Dalits and the Tribals. The focus is not on the centre but the margins, reading between the lines, re-interpreting the narratives for our times to bring about green revolution through ecological conversion, and building an environmentally just society.

This should not be another article/research findings/paper/papal document to refer to later to write research papers but ought to act as an action plan. The action plan is the synthesis of five da’s:

1. ‘**Dama**’ (discipline): Humans need to discipline their greed, share the resources. This also entails change in life-style, production, and consumption.
2. ‘**Dāna**’ (Give): Humans need to give back to nature, and nurture nature. Give to the distressed.
3. ‘**Dakṣa**’ (Vigilant): Humans need to be alive and

vigilant to the environmental degradation.

4. ‘**Diśā**’ (Direction): Social justice ethics has to be the guiding principle; direction.
5. ‘**Dayā**’ (Compassion): Being kind to others includes being kind to nature. Nature’s welfare and human welfare cannot be separated from each other. If we are kind to nature, we will naturally be kind to one another.

The action plan proposed is *destined to develop a dike* that is in *dharma* achieved through *dialogue* inclusive of *Demeter* because of the *dúrdṛṣṭi* of the Supreme Pontiff in *Laudato Si*. Thus, the creation shall sing exultantly, “**Praise be to You, my Lord!**”

Notes

1. Reid, Barbara. Paul for the Ecozoic Age. *The Ecological Challenge*, 1994: 16.
2. Cantic of the Creatures, in *Francis of Assisi: Early Documents*, vol. 1, New York-London-Manila, 1999: 113.
3. King, Ursula. *Feminist Theology from the Third World: A Reader*. Maryknoll, New York. 1994: 61.
4. Reid, Barbara. Paul for the Ecozoic Age. *The Ecological Challenge*, 1994: 20.
5. Bolivian Bishops’ Conference, Pastoral Letter on the Environment and Human Development in Bolivia El universo, don de Dios para la vida (23 March 2012), 17.
6. Marx, Reinhard Cardinal. “Everything is connected:” On the Relevance of an Integral Understanding of Reality in *Laudato Si*. *Theological Studies*, Vol 77, Issue 2, 2016:295.
7. Celermajer, Danielle. The Prospects and Conditions for a New Dialogue for the Planet: A Response to *laudato Si*. *St Mark’s Review*, No. 236, Aug. 2016: 65.

Homily Notes

March 4, 2018: III Sunday of Lent

Exodus 20: 1-17; 1 Cor 1: 22-25; John 2: 13-25.

Experiencing Love of God

Once a Zen guru told to a new comer: when you are in a journey to join in Buddhism, if the Buddha comes against you, then you must kill the Buddha and continue the journey. Otherwise you will begin to worship and spend time for him. Consequently you forget the real Buddha who really lives in your mind. In this gospel passage we can see an angry Jesus, instead of a merciful and kind Jesus. If we look at the context of this incident, we can see that it was not the anger, but a deep mourning of Jesus for His loving Father. Israel was His beloved children but they did not show their love and affection to their Father. God once spoke to them, "I am the Lord, Your God, who brought you out of the land of Egypt, out of the house of slavery: you shall have no other God before me" (ex: 20-2). But what happened to them actually they built a temple for Him. They started worshipping Him through the sacrifice. This brought a lot of wealth for them. When wealth and power accumulated in their hands through these rituals, their hearts slowly diverted to wealth, rather than God. They started to gain more wealth in the name of their Yahweh. They gave the holy place for trade. They started to bargain in the name of God. God became a matter of money. This is why Jesus took a revolutionary step. Dear friends, it can happen in our life also. God loves us very much. But sometimes the attraction of worldly worldly happiness can draw a veil before his unlimited love. Sometimes we will go behind the extreme ritual to please God. If we can't see the true love of Jesus in the people around

us, then all these things are worthless. So believe and experience in the true love of God. Because, as St. Paul says, for those who are called, Christ is the power of God and wisdom of God (1 Cor:1:24). -**Amal**

March 11, 2018 : IV Sunday of Lent

2 Chronicles 36: 14-16, 19-23; Eph 2: 4-10; John 3: 14-21.

Be Faithful to God

In 2 Chro 36:14-16, 19-23 we find that the heads of the priesthood including people of God had done all shameful practices of the nation and defile the temple of Jerusalem. They did not change their evil practices and behavior in spite of prophet's interventions to their sinful ways of life. Their infidelity to God led them to sin after sin and finally it caused burning of the temple of God and demolition of the walls of Jerusalem once that was their security.

Even though people go astray from the Lord but God never gives up. He accompanies them in their every moment of life and each step they take because He loves the humanity so much. Therefore, he sent his only son to draw us out of sin and bring us to life. We are called to lead a good life in Christ. Because it is not through our own merit, but through grace and faith in Jesus Christ that we are saved. As baptized Christians we are called children of light and through our life of love, mercy, compassion, respect and forgiveness we need to keep the Christian identity intact. If we do commit sins or fall into temptations but do not turn back to God with repentant heart we become children of darkness or Satan. When we linger to such kind of life we kill our own self and conscience thus we become lovers of night or dark.

Today through our sinful thoughts, words and deeds we fail to promote life of self and of others. Therefore, let us be mindful that we are the temple of God and keep our heart pure so that God's reign may be established in our heart and life too. -**Sunil Kujur**

March 18, 2018: V Sunday of Lent

Jer 31: 31-34; Heb 5: 7-9; Joh 12: 20-33

Drawing All People to Himself

“When I am lifted up from the earth,” he said, “I will draw everyone to myself” (John 12:32). These words, which are so full of promise and hope, show us that Jesus didn’t come just to forgive our sins. He also came to bring us into a relationship with him. He came so that we could be “drawn” to him and “lifted up” with him to the presence of his heavenly Father.

Lift Up Your Heart! The story of Abraham and Isaac can help us understand just how much God wants to lift us up. More than two thousand years after God spared Abraham’s only son, Isaac, he chose not to spare his only Son, Jesus—even after Jesus prayed that “this cup” would pass him by (Mat 26:39). Surely God loved his Son even more deeply than Abraham loved Isaac. But he loved us so much—and so did his Son—that he freely gave him up for us. God’s willingness to sacrifice his only Son for us demonstrates the lengths to which he will go to save us, to teach us, and to lift us up to his side.

At every Mass, we are invited: “Lift up your hearts,” and we respond by saying, “We lift them up to the Lord.” What do you think would happen if each of us used this moment to actually do just that? What would the church look like if we all set our position at every Eucharist, saying, “Jesus, I want to be drawn closer to you. I don’t want anything to get in the way. Come, Lord, and lift all of us up so that we can know you better and love you more.” (https://wau.org/archives/article/i_will_lift_you_up/)

March 25, 2018 : Palm Sunday of the Lord’s Passion

Isa. 50:4-7; Philip. 2:6-11; Mk 14:1-15:47

Lord, Come and Save us

We begin the ‘Holy Week’ of our Lord’s Passion, Death and Resurrection from today. This year we had our Ash Wednesday on Valentine’s Day and Easter coincides with April fool. What a coincidence? Yet it has a beautiful message for us. “Blessed is He who comes in the name of the Lord!” The crowd exclaimed joyfully at Jesus as he entered Jerusalem. A beautiful welcome for the Lord. In remembrance of Jesus’ triumphant entry to Jerusalem we celebrate today Palm Sunday. In our liturgy especially in the songs we sing today by waving our olive and palm branches we have expressed our praise and our joy, our desire to receive Jesus who comes to us, singing “Hosanna”. We marked this Lenten season beginning by saying, “Jesus, you are my valentine!” What does Hosanna signify? The meaning of the word is SAVE US, WE PRAY. By acclaiming it from our heart we are asking Jesus to come and save us. The Gospel passage narrates how he saved us. It was a saving from the clutches of sin. For that Jesus had to go through a terrible passion – not only in his body, but emotionally too. In the long proclamation of passion narration from the Gospel according to Mark, we listen to how the enemies plot against Jesus, the betrayal by Judas and denial by Peter, standing for trial and acquitted for a crime which he has not done, mocking and ridiculing by the Roman soldiers, the walk to Calvary in the way of the cross and finally the crucifixion. Jesus’ passion is summed up in his cry on cross – Eloi, Eloi, lema sabachthani, My God, My God, why have you forgotten me? It is a prayer of the one who entrusts everything to God, the father. It is not a cry out of desperation. It is a recitation of Psalm 22 which is the psalm given as the responsorial psalm. Jesus had to suffer for our salvation. Suffering is not without gain. It brings transformation. In our sufferings we are called and invited to adhere to the pain of the Lord so that it becomes salvific to us and the people around us. It is when we persevere in our suffering to stay closer to the lord, we declare our faith. The lord will not desert us or give up on us even when there had been times where we denied him like peter. True repentance will bring us closer to him. Many of us experience doubt, especially on April 1 for the fear of being fooled. Easter is not such a message. Even the disciples didn’t believe it

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at first and ran to the tomb to find Jesus. Yet the Risen Christ became an experience to them and their fear was transformed into joy. Our fears and failures will be transformed in Christ. In him we have a sure foundation. In that faith our singing “Hosanna” will become meaningful. Lord, Come and Save us! **-Rejin**

April 1, 2018: Easter Sunday

Acts 10: 34, 11:37-43; Col. 3:1-4, Jn. 20:1-9

Christ has Conquered All

Easter is the greatest and the most important feast in the Church. The Resurrection of Christ is the basis of our Christian Faith. It marks the birthday of our eternal hope. It is the greatest of the miracles - it proves that Jesus is God. That is why St. Paul writes: “If Christ has not been raised, then our preaching is in vain; and your Faith is in vain..” (I Cor 15:14). If Jesus Christ did not rise from the dead, then the Church is a fraud and faith is a sham. All the basic doctrines of Christianity are founded on the truth of the Resurrection. “Jesus is Lord; He is risen!” (Rom 10:9) was the central theme of the kerygma (“preaching”), of the apostles.

Firstly, Easter is a feast which gives us hope and encouragement in this world of suffering, sorrow and tears. It reminds us that life is worth living. It is our belief in the Real Presence of the Risen Jesus in our souls, in His Church, in the Blessed Sacrament and in Heaven that gives meaning to our personal, as well as to our common, prayers. Our trust in the all-pervading presence of the Risen Lord gives us strength to fight against temptations and freedom from unnecessary worries and fears.

Secondly, we are to be Resurrection people. It gives us the joyful message that we are a “Resurrection people.” This means that we are not supposed to remain buried in the tomb of our sins, evil habits and dangerous addictions. It gives us the Good News that no tomb can hold us down anymore - not the tomb of despair, discouragement, doubt or death itself. Instead, we are expected

to live a joyful and peaceful life, constantly experiencing the real presence of the Risen Lord in all the events of our lives.

Thirdly, we need to seek our peace and joy in the Risen Jesus. The living presence of the Risen Lord gives us lasting peace and celestial joy in the face of the boredom, suffering, pain and tensions of our day-to-day life. “Peace be with you” was Jesus’ salutation to his disciples at all post-Resurrection appearances. For the true Christian, every day must be an Easter Day lived joyfully in the close company of the Risen Lord. Finally we need to remember Easter in our Good Fridays. Easter reminds us that every Good Friday in our lives will have an Easter Sunday, and that Jesus will let us share the power of his Resurrection. Each time we display our love of others, we share in the Resurrection. Each time we face a betrayal of trust and, with God’s grace, forgive the betrayer, we share in the Resurrection of Jesus. Each time we fail in our attempts to ward off temptations but keep on trying to overcome them, we share in the Resurrection. Each time we continue to hope even when our hope seems unanswered, we share in the power of Jesus’ Resurrection. In short, the message of Easter is that nothing can destroy us; not pain, rejection, betrayal or death, because Christ has conquered all these, and we, too, can conquer them if we put our Faith and trust in the Risen Lord. Amen. **-Ciril Vallomkunnel**

April 8, 2018: II Sunday of Easter

Act: 4: 32-35; 1 John 5: 1-6; John 20: 19-31.

Faith in Risen Christ

The liturgy of the word is inviting us to reflect upon the theme “Faith in Risen Christ.” However, it points out a vivid picture as to what the early church aspired. More than some utopian dream, these verses should serve as a standard by which our churches today might be measured. “They held all of their possessions “in common.” The disciples of Jesus were very much energetic in

witnessing about the resurrection of the Lord Jesus, and great grace was upon them all. We too are being invited to have the great desire to proclaim the resurrection of Jesus Christ. Having given up everything, we can own Christ as our wealth and power. The disciples were being filled with the power of Holy Spirit. Thus, “everyone who believes that Jesus is the Christ has been born of God and everyone who loves the parent loves the Child. (1 John 5:1). To be an unthematic Christians or Disciples of Christ one need to have deep faith in Christ Himself. We are called to love one another. This is the way that we will be recognized as true Christians or a true disciples of Christ. Today, the life of a religious has become very indifferent in following of Jesus. We need to give up our sinful ways and obey His very commandments. When we obey his statues and make an intimate relationship with Him, then we become true Disciples of Christ. Once we become the true disciples of Christ then we are able to project ourselves that have conquers the whole world. This love of God precedes the gospel passage that centered on the Christ’s invitation “peace be with you.”

However, when we read this passage it is easy for us to single out Thomas as the doubting fearful disciple but the truth is that they were all hiding fearfully behind locked doors. Similar to the shadows of our lives wall, the disciples had some rather large and looming “monsters” in their hearts and minds as well. The gospel paints a picture of the resurrection’s hope and power. A dark grave and a mighty stone can’t keep Jesus out either. He appears in the midst of doubt, fear, hopelessness and the falling darkness of evening with peace. Similar to us inviting our fearful daughter to the comfort of our big safe bed, Jesus comes into the darkness and chaos and binds it with peace. He comes into our darkness and chaos still today. When we can no longer cover up our cracks of human brokenness with lies. He stands among us and speaks the peace of the resurrection and invites us to believe that he is Lord. Let’s believe that Christ is risen from dead and is with us today and forever. We need the inner peace in our hearts. Hence, it will bring to us the rest in the warmth and comfort of

the son who brings peace to those who believe in Him. **-Binod Hembrom**

April 15, 2018: III Sunday of Easter

Acts 3:13-15; 1John 2:1-5a; Lk 24:35-48.

Risen Lord as Source of Peace

Jesus our Lord, the author of Life and our Creator of the Universe was and is among us. St. Peter, in the first reading, speaks to the people from the Solomon’s portico that they executed the author of Life. However, he was raised by God. He invites them to repent for what they had done in ignorance and have faith in Jesus who will give them life in abundance and forgive their sins for what they had done. In the second reading we have St. John giving us hope by signifying that we have an advocate with the Father not only for our sins but for the whole word. We have an obligation to follow his commandments and all the more to have faith in him. The one who has faith in him will have life. And in the gospel we find, Jesus’ appearance to the disciples but they are terrified and startled looking at Jesus thinking that they were seeing a ghost. All the three readings of today invite us to ensure our strong faith in Christ Jesus, as an advocate for Peace and all the more as our Lord and saviour.

Do I really believe in Jesus and in his words? Or am I terrified when He appears? St Theresa of Kolkata said, “We need to find God and he cannot be found in sounds and restlessness. We need to be silenced and touch the souls.” Let us find risen Lord within us for he came for all and to establish peace on earth. Let us question ourselves the source of peace around me or cause for the disharmony? **-Agnel Baretto**

April 22, 2018: IV Sunday of Easter

Acts.4:8-12; 1 John 3: 1-2; John 10:11-18

Shepherd with the Smell of Sheep

Love is above everything in the world and the ultimate expression of love is sacrifice. This is what Jesus taught us through His

life. The readings of today also talk about this unending love of God. In Acts we see Peter being filled with the spirit of God and courageously preaching about the risen Lord and says that only through Him everyone can be saved. All the miracles they do is also by the power of Jesus whom they have crucified. The gospel also speaks about Jesus who loves everyone. He says that He is the good shepherd and a good shepherd will sacrifice his life for his sheep. Because he loves them as his own. He is not like a servant or a butcher who is primarily concerned about himself. He loves them from his heart. So that he is ready to do anything for them, even to sacrifice his own life for them if any wolves or any other animal come to attack them. Each of the sheep is important to him and therefore he protects them so carefully without being separated from the group. Another characteristic of a good shepherd is that he knows everyone of him personally. He calls them by their name. He can identify them by their voice. This shows the attachment that he has with them. He is very close to them and therefore he cannot leave them.

The love of God towards us also is like that of a good shepherd. He knows each one of us and protects us with His divine providence. He is with us wherever we go and guide us in our actions. Understanding this fact King David prayed that “God is my shepherd and I shall not want” (Ps.23:1). The question before us is the same. Are we recognizing the love of that good shepherd who loves us abundantly? Are we ready to proclaim Jesus to others like David and Peter in our lives too? When he loves us He also desires that we must be faithful to Him. Let us try to be the good sheep who understands the mind of the shepherd and follow Him as he wishes. -**Jithin**

April 29, 2018: V Sunday of Easter

Acts 9: 26-31; 1 John 3: 18-24; John 15:1-8

Call to be with Jesus

Today, God is asking us through these readings that where are you? Are you with me?.....

Everyone is called and chosen by God. As Christians we are all members of one body, the Church, and “we have been grafted onto Christ as members and have become temples of the Holy Spirit (1 cor 6:19). On the other hand Jesus Christ to whom we are attached in terms attached to His Father too. Here one could see a flow of unbroken relationship that’s started from God as a father to the son and to his people or church who are temples of Holy Spirit. Therefore, it is a call to abide in Jesus or in this Trinitarian communion of Love. This communitarian aspect is very much portrayed in the Gospel of today. Jesus is the true vine and we are the branches and Father is the vine grower and we see if the branch is not producing any fruit then the vine grower cuts away that branches or if it is not producing sufficiently, then the vine grower prunes that branches.

Therefore we as branches of the vine are called to produce fruits. What is that fruits? Which is explained in today’s second reading, that is love one another in truth and action. We can produce this fruit if only we obey the commandments given by God the Father. First reading shows very concretely the result obeying such command that is “the church throughout Judea, Galilee and Samaria had peace and was built up. Living in the fear of the Lord and in the comfort of the Holy Spirit it creased in numbers”. Here we see church was growing because it was built in the strong foundations of love and truth such foundations will be unshaken even in times of difficulties and problems. Therefore all the three readings first of all calling us to be with Jesus, secondly love others in truth and actions, thirdly let others see you as a point of attraction to Christ himself. - **Tony**

May 6, 2018: VI Sunday of Easter

Acts 10: 25-26, 34-35, 44-48 & 1 Jn 4: 7-10; Jn 15: 9-17

Being Loved

Christ’s greatest command, according to the Gospel of John, is that we love one another as Christ has loved us. When we think about the implications of such a love we may quietly admit to

ourselves, “I could never love others to the full extent that Jesus loves me.” Can anyone actually fulfill this commandment?

In the passage that precedes Jesus’ command to “Love each other, as I have loved you” Jesus speaks about the foundation of that love. In John 15:1ff He says, “I am the true vine; you are the branches... Abide in me... and bear much fruit...”

There’s something fundamentally important about the concept of a vine or a vineyard in Israelite thought. The vine has become a symbol of Israel as the people of God. Israel is pictured in the Old Testament writings as the vineyard or the vine of God.

When Jesus made the statement, “I am the true vine”, we can just see all of their defenses go up.

Jesus was actually saying to them, “Listen my friend, you think that you are a branch and a vine just because you belong to the people of Israel. You think that you are the real thing just because you are a part of a special nation... because of your birth and nationality.”

The prophets saw a vine that was in desperate need of pruning. And they were right. Again and again the people of Israel strayed from their intended purpose as God’s chosen people. Jesus, however, has a legitimate claim to the title of “true vine”, because his fruits were rooted in the power of God. Israel had lost its rootedness in God their Savior.

But Jesus was firmly rooted in the love of God. Jesus was firmly established in an intimate living fellowship with God and faith in God. His actions and teachings had their life-source in God’s love. The secret of the life of Jesus was his connectedness with God. He withdrew regularly into a solitary place to meet and have fellowship with God. Jesus was always abiding in God.

“As the Father has loved me, so have I loved you...”, says Jesus in verse 9. That begs the question, “How, exactly, did Jesus experience His Father’s love?” What did he get from God in exchange for his obedience?

But, we know also that the heavenly Father gave his son Jesus an infinite sense of belonging and being rooted in his love. “You are my beloved son in whom I am well pleased”, we hear the blessing spoken at the time of his baptism. God gave Jesus a firm foundation... the conviction of His Presence, his counsel and his faithfulness in times of trial and temptation. Jesus received from His heavenly Father a peace that far transcends the restlessness of this world. The Father’s love assured him of a sense of security and safety (Geborgenheit) in a harsh world.

That is the affirmation that we too can experience through the love of Jesus. “As the Father has loved me, so I have loved you...” As we experience the love of Jesus, we are the recipients of a love that goes far beyond material things. It is a love that transcends human comprehension. It is a love that cannot be earned... a love that knows no boundaries... A love that we couldn’t get if we chose it...

The secret of Christ’s claim that he is the true vine lies in his connectedness with God. We too are a part of this wonderful vine as we remain/abide in Christ. In Jesus God has chosen us to for his divine purpose, namely for Joy, for expressing act of love, to be his friends, and to be his advertisements.

May we, as friends and partners, rooted in Christ bear much fruit as we obey the command to love. Let us abide in Christ and bring forth the richest fruits of his blessing. (<https://sermons.faithlife.com/sermons/113759-john-159-17-commanded-to-love>)

May 13, 2018: The Ascension of the Lord

Acts 1: 1-11; Eph 1: 17-23; Mk 16: 15-29

Receiving His Grace Trustfully

Generally, when any one of our family members goes abroad and returns with money and costly gifts, we might be tempted to ask: “Can you take us abroad with you and get us a job? The person is likely to reply that it is not very easy to get a job abroad.

Then, the person will give a long explanation that, to get a job, one needs to work hard, needs to learn the skills, needs to have patience, needs to have self-discipline, etc., etc. While all these explanations are going on, the person who listens gets tired. But, only one who is really dedicated and is prepared to work very hard can hope to go through the grind and one day become like the one who has got a job abroad.

In today's readings, we hear a similar story where Jesus' disciples look up to him when he is ascended. Today, through the readings the Lord is telling us that we need to work hard to become disciples of our Lord in order to proclaim his Word to the ends of the earth.

Today's first reading speaks about Ascension of the Lord. Here we see Jesus giving three gifts to the believers and to his disciples: (a) the gift of the Holy Spirit, (b) the gift of spreading good news to the ends of the world, and, (c) the gift of the return of Jesus. Here we see a particular name 'Theophilus' which means "lover of God" or person who loves God. We see his name in the gospel of Luke 1:3. The only book which speaks about the duration of 40 days between resurrection and ascension of Christ is the 'Acts of the Apostles'. This number, forty, reminds us of the Israelites in the wilderness for 40 years, and 40 days of the fasting of Jesus Christ. So generally, the number 4 or 40 refers to universality and completeness as we see here the risen Lord spending 40 days with his disciples to strengthen them, to fill them with his Holy Spirit and to make them aware of his mission. Christ instructed them to baptize with the Holy Spirit and preach the good news to the ends of the earth. For example Acts 8:12 "when people believed Philip, who was proclaiming the good news about the kingdom of God and in the name of Jesus Christ, they were baptized both men and women". We also see that Christ is taken up into heaven along with two men. These two men could be two angels or either Moses and Elijah. Here the Lord taken up in the clouds refers to the glory and presence of the Lord. The cloud has a specific meaning as seen in Exodus 40:39 – "Then the cloud covered the tent of meeting and the glory of the Lord filled the

Tabernacle". This reminds us that as the Lord was taken up in glory; today lord is calling us to live an upright life, where at this moment disciples started to look upwards, which indicates that one day we would be the citizens of heaven.

In the second reading we see Christ blessing each of us with different gifts and graces; we see this in Verse 11 and also in 1st Cor 12:4-11. Brothers and sisters, each of us is blessed with different graces and it's time to analyze whether we use these for the development of our ministry or for our own development. In Psalm 68:18 God assures his graces to both believers and non-believers, so that one day we will use them for the betterment of the kingdom of God.

We see Jesus taken up into heaven and sitting at the right hand of God, the Father. In II Kings 2:11 we see Elijah taken up into the whirlwind. In Luke 24:51 we also see Lord taken up into heaven. In Psalm 110: 1 Jesus is seen sitting at the right hand of the Father "The Lord says to my Lord, 'Sit at my right hand until I make your enemies your footstool'". In Ephesians 1:20 we see "God put this power to work in Christ when he raised him up from the dead and seated him at his great power".

The gospel reading clearly calls each of us today to repent and live a just life; and to get baptized in the name of Jesus so that we might inherit his kingdom, where he sits at the right hand of God, the Father. Today's gospel instructs us to "go therefore and make disciples of all nations, baptize them in the name of the Father, Son and Holy Spirit" (Mt 28:19). It reminds us in 1st Peter 3:21 that those who are baptized will inherit the kingdom of God and John 3:18b tells those who don't believe will be condemned. This reminds us of our mission of proclaiming and baptizing so that people might be saved.

We are all invited to participate in the mystery of the Ascension of the Lord. We are all invited to sit before the Lord who sits at the right hand of the Father. This happens only, when we bear each other in love, maturity and patience. We become part of God's kingdom when we utilize our blessings and graces in

bringing the kingdom of God down, here-and-now. In this holy Eucharist let us ask Christ; to strengthen us to proclaim his good news to all the ends of the earth... Amen -**Anand**

May 20, 2018: Pentecost Sunday

Acts 2: 1-11; 1Corinthians 12: 3-7, 12-13; John 20: 19-23

Love, Life and Holiness

The church was made manifest to the world on the Pentecost by the outpouring of the Holy Spirit. The gift of the spirit ushers in new era in dispensation of the mystery – the age of church, during which Christ manifests, makes present and communicates his work of salvation through the liturgy of his church, ‘until he comes’. In this age of the church Christ now lives and acts in and with his church, in a new way appropriate to this new age.

There are three basic elements marking the event: the sound of a mighty wind, tongue of fire and the charism of speaking in other languages. All these three elements are rich in symbolic meaning. First, the sound of a mighty wind. In Hebrew as in Greek, “wind” is a synonym of “spirit”. It also means “breath”. In the bible a strong wind announces the presence of God. It is the sign of theophany. The second element of the Pentecost event is fire. ‘Divided tongues as of fire appeared among them’. Fire is always present in the manifestations of God in the Old Testament. We see this in the covenant between God and Abraham. The memory of the special manifestation of God in the form of fire was alive in the soul of Israel. St. Paul tells us in the second reading of the liturgy of word. The third element marking the event of Pentecost, tongues of fire and the charism of speaking in other tongues. The words that come from the Holy Spirit are like fire. In this we see Holy Spirit is giving himself to people, produces in them an effect which is both real and symbolic. The symbolism of multiplication of languages is very significant. According to the bible the diversity of languages was the sign of the multiplication of peoples and nations and indeed of their dispersal following on

the construction of the tower of Babel. The word “Babel’ means confusion.

In the church, language is not a barrier. The people gathered around the upper room asked: “are not all these who are speaking Galileans? And how is it that we hear, each of us in our own native tongue? We hear them speaking out God’s deeds of power: so the Holy Spirit is person, the Holy Spirit is breath, wind and fire. The Holy Spirit is gift, grace, and glory. The Holy Spirit is openness, power and activity. The Holy Spirit is love, life and holiness. - **Kumar**

May 27, 2018: The Solemnity of the Most Holy Trinity

Dt 4:32-34, 39-40; Rom 8:14-17; Mt 28:16-20

Relevance of the Doctrine of Trinity

Is the doctrine of the Trinity relevant today? If Christianity were simply a religion of keeping the law, the inner life of the lawgiver would not matter. But if Christianity is about personal relationship with God, then who God really is matters totally. Common sense tells us that some supreme being made the universe and that we owe Him homage. But that the creator is a trinity of persons who invites us to intimate friendship with Himself.

God Is Love: A Community of Three Persons: God is love, says 1 John 4:8. If God were solitary, how could he have been love before he created the world? Who would there have been to love? Jesus reveals a God who is eternally a community of three persons pouring themselves out in love for one another. The Father does not create the Son and then, with the Son, create the Spirit. No, the Father eternally generates the Son. And with and through the Son, this Father eternally “breathes” the Spirit as a sort of personalized sigh of love. “As it was in the beginning, is now and ever shall be.” That’s what the conclusion of the Glory Be really means, that the self-giving of the three divine persons did not begin at a moment in time, but was, is, and is to come.

We in God’s Image & Likeness: If we are truly to “know” our God, we must know this. But if we are ever to understand our-

selves, we must also know this. For we were made in the image and likeness of God, and God is a community of self-donating love. That means that we can never be happy isolated from others, protecting ourselves from others, holding ourselves back selfishly from others. Unless we give ourselves in love, we can never be fully human. And unless we participate in the life of God's people, we can never be truly Christian either. Because Christianity is about building up the community of divine love which is called the Church.

The family, the domestic Church, is a reflection of trinitarian love – the love of husband and wife, distinct and very different persons, generates the child who is from them but is nonetheless distinct from them, indeed absolutely unique.

Personhood: Dignity, Individuality, Freedom: One of the greatest treasures of Western culture is the concept of the uniqueness and dignity of the individual person. The concept of the irreplaceable uniqueness of each person came into Western culture straight from the doctrine of the Trinity, three who possess the exact same divine nature but who are yet irreplaceably unique in their personhood. (www.crossroadsinitiative.com)

June 3, 2018: The Most Holy Body and Blood of Christ

Exodus 24: 3-8, Hebrews 9:11-15, Mark 14: 12-16, 22-26

The Mystery of Eucharist

“Take, this is my body..... He took a cup, and after giving thanks he gave it to them, saying, ‘This is my blood of the covenant, which is poured out for many’ (Mk.14: 22-24).

Eucharist: The Fullness of God's Love: Today, we are in a world of celebrations. Celebrations begin with the birth of a child and continue with his or her baptism, confirmation, wedding and even for death anniversaries. It was also the customary of the Jews to celebrate ‘the feast of the Passover’ in Jerusalem even coming from far away cities as pilgrims. The feast of the Pass-

over is celebrated on the 15th of the month of Nisan according to the Jewish calendar. This is in view of remembering the blessings and mercy that Yahweh has shown to Israel while they were under Egyptian slavery.

In the first part of the Gospel reading, we see the disciples enquiring to Jesus where to make preparation to celebrate their Passover feast. As Jesus knew that it was his last supper with the disciples and he was to hand over himself to the authorities on the following day and be crucified, he had made enough preparations earlier and only asked his two disciples to make sure that an upper room to be ready to have their Passover meal.

In the second part of the Gospel, we see some unusual things happening during the Passover meal. Jesus takes a loaf of bread, gives thanks, blesses and breaks it and gives to them saying that it is his body. He repeats the same procedure with the cup of wine saying that it is the blood of the new covenant which is poured out for many. In Hebrew ‘Rab - many’, means all. We know that these are the words of consecration which we hear in the Eucharistic celebration when the bread and wine become the body and blood of Jesus through transubstantiation. The four actions that Jesus performed here has great theological significance. Taking the bread symbolizes that he is not compelled but willingly accepts to be handed over to the authorities and be crucified. Secondly, he gives thanks to the father because of his assurance that the whole humanity will be saved from their transgressions of sin by the blood that he is going to shed as an expiation. Thirdly, the verb ‘break’ signifies that he will be crucified on the cross and fourthly, the act of giving implies the love Jesus had for his own disciples who represent humanity. Through these theologically significant actions, Jesus desired that all humanity should take part in the redemption that was offered through his own kenosis, self-emptying on the cross. Consequently no one is exempted from the salvation.

In the first reading, we see the ritual of the first covenant, the covenant that was conditional. However, Yahweh establishes

his covenant with them to be their God and Israel His chosen race only when they accepted to obey the commandments of the Lord. As a sign of the covenant, Moses sprinkles the blood of the animal that is being sacrificed on the altar and the people. In the Gospel reading, when Jesus says that the cup of wine is offered to many, it becomes a sacrificial offering reminding a new covenant; a covenant that unites between him and the entire humanity. In the new covenant, Jesus does not put any condition but embraces the entire humanity through his kenotic love.

If blood is used conventionally as a medium of expiation that was mediated only through the high priest who could enter into the Holy of Holies only on the day of Yom Kippur, the day of atonement. We see in the second reading that Christ himself comes as high priest from the order of Melchizedek entering into the Holy of Holies by sacrificing his own blood for the eternal redemption and liberating us from all the transgressions.

Dear friends, as we celebrate the Eucharist, what is important is to enter into the mystery dimension of the Eucharist and feel the depth of the love of God manifested in the Eucharist. As St. John Maria Vianney says, "If we really understand the mystery of the Eucharist, we would die of joy".

At this juncture, we ask ourselves, whether we are able to break ourselves and to offer ourselves to the other, especially to those who are in most need, and thus to become a selfless person, a kenotic person for others. Let us pray that we may understand the mystery of the Eucharist and get nourished through our active participation in it. Amen -**Shebin C.S**

June 10, 2018: X Sunday in Ordinary Time

Gn 3: 9-15; 2 Cor 4: 13-5:1; Mk 3:20-35

Reaction of Jesus' Relatives

The New Testament preserves evidence suggesting that Jesus' relationship with his family was rather strained. An important source is Mark 3:21, which says: "When his family heard what was happening, they came to take control of him. They were

saying, 'He's out of his mind!'" (translation: Common English Bible).

Yet, Christian tradition has had a difficult time reckoning with the perhaps troubling idea of family strife between Jesus and his kin. Consider what translators and even other Gospel authors have done with Mark 3:21:

- The King James Version totally removes Jesus' family from this part of the scene, saying: "And when his friends heard of it, they went out to lay hold on him: for they said, 'He is beside himself.'"
- The New Revised Standard Version puts the disparagement of Jesus in the mouths of others, saying: "When his family heard it, they went out to restrain him, for people were saying, 'He has gone out of his mind.'"
- The authors of the Gospels according to Matthew and Luke, whose books were produced after the Gospel according to Mark and who included scenes similar to Mark 3:20-35, omitted from their narratives any suggestion that Jesus' family thought he was crazy.

The story told in the wider context, Mark 3:20-35, sets Jesus' family in comparison to influential religious leaders (legal scholars based in Jerusalem). Both groups express an inability to understand who Jesus really is. The religious authorities conclude he is possessed by Satan. His family assumes he has lost his sanity. In an ancient setting, these diagnoses were roughly equivalent to each other.

The scene underscores how those who presumably were in great positions to make sense of Jesus still were not immediately able to see him as God's agent. As Jesus announced and re-inaugurated God's intentions for human flourishing, many could not overcome the disorienting character of his message. Even close relatives and religious insiders were bewildered by what he said, which threatened to disrupt so many aspects of human society (Matthew L Skinner, *Huffington Post*).

June 17, 2018: XI Sunday in Ordinary Time

Ezekiel, 17:22-24; 2 Cor. 5:6-10; Mk. 4:26-34

Focus to Please the Lord

In today's readings Jesus invites us to redirect our focus on the Kingdom of God and to change the course of our actions. What is really the kingdom of God? Is it the same as the earthly kingdoms? The kingdom of God is the reign of God. It is the life in which God's will govern our actions and He becomes the centre of our lives. Through today's readings God gives us the clear image of the Kingdom of God. The first reading from the Ezekiel, 17: 22-24, we get an optimistic prophesy and a grace note on the exultation of Israel. It is a portrait of the peaceful kingdom where amid the great cedar's branches every bird nests in safety. This portrays Yahweh's unrivalled sovereignty over the history. The Kingdom of God or the reign of God will be established according to His will. Human effort cannot delay or hasten its coming.

The two parables about seeds - the parable of the seed of growing itself and the parable of the mustard seed in today's Gospel also reveals the secret of the kingdom of God. The parable suggests that the kingdom of God can be present like the seed prior to the appearance of the ripe fruit. No one notices its presence until it is fully revealed. But, once it is revealed it is easily noticeable. The seed growing secretly is a call for being alert about the suddenness of the coming judgement. "Be alert; I have told you everything" (Mk. 13:23). The kingdom of God or the reign of God is there in our midst. Many a times we fail to recognise this in our struggles and sufferings. In the time of God, the kingdom that has been hidden will be manifested. The parable of the mustard seed reveals God's protection covers our lives irrespective our life situations.

Is this experience of the kingdom of God and His protection simply a future promise? It is not a future promise The Kingdom of God can be found by us in our present day experience of God's protection and care. It gives us a certainty and hope for God's protection in our sufferings

Does the passiveness of the human figures lead us to be simply idle waiting for the establishment of God's kingdom with the end of sufferings? No. The passivity of the human figures reminds us that the experience of the kingdom of God is a gracious gift of God. But, He invites human effort and participation to live the kingdom values like faith, hope, love, forgiveness etc. and thereby share the experience of God's kingdom. It calls for continuous redirection of our lives to the focus of the kingdom and a rededication to the commitment to God. St. Paul gives two keys for living with focus on the kingdom of God in the reading from 2-Corinthians, 5:6-10. One is to orient our lives to the Lord than to our body remembering our life here on earth as in a temporary tent and the other one is to do the acts pleasing to the Lord. So, our present life should be a life toward Christ with the hope of eternal home.

Paulo Coelho reminds us in his best seller 'The Alchemist', "We are travellers on a cosmic journey, star dust, swirling and dancing in the eddies and whirlpools of infinity. Life is eternal. We have stopped for a moment. It is a little parenthesis in eternity". So, when we loses this understanding and this focus what guides us is the craving to fulfil the bodily desires that cannot be fully satisfied. Can our smartphones replace God? Can the junk food satisfy our hunger forever? Can we enjoy the real happiness becoming a millionaire? No. As we read in 'The Alchemist', "A truly happy man is a man who carries God within him and the happiness can be found in a simple grain of desert land. We read in Matthew, 6:33, "But, strive first for the kingdom of God and His righteousness and all these things will be given to you as well". Again we read in Mt. 16:26, "For what it will profit them if they gain the whole world but forfeit their life? Or what will they give in return for their life?" The growth of the kingdom of God and the work of God is there in our midst. Let us not become blind by closing our eyes to it. Let us not forget that the body and spirit are designed to honour God and the temples of God's presence. So, our destiny is to please the Lord, do His will living out

the kingdom values with the full focus on the eternal home. May God bless us to live in the Spirit. Amen. -Tony

June 24, 2018: Solemnity of Nativity of Saint John the Baptist

Is 49:1-6; Acts 13:22-26; Lk 1:57-66, 80

St John the Baptist as Witness to Jesus

St. John the Baptist was the last and greatest of the Old Testament prophets sent to “prepare the way of the Lord.” Jesus called him the greatest of all the prophets because of his direct involvement in the earthly life and ministry of the Messiah.

St. John the Baptist, Forerunner of Jesus: In St. John the Baptist, the Old Testament meets the New Testament: Before his time, the Law and the Prophets were proclaimed; from his life and to the end of time, the Gospel of Christ is proclaimed.

We remember Saint John the Baptist each time we pray the Holy Rosary, our prayerful meditations on the life of Christ. In the Second Joyful Mystery, the Visitation, the Virgin Mary went in haste to visit her cousin Elizabeth following the Annunciation. John the Baptist leaped in the womb of his mother, Saint Elizabeth, as soon as they were greeted by the Virgin Mary, who then was pregnant with the Child Jesus. We also remember St. John the Baptist in the First Luminous Mystery, as he was the one who baptized Jesus in Jordan river.

St. John the Baptist was from the womb until his death a witness to Jesus Christ as the Messiah and Son of God. At the greeting of the pregnant Mother of God to his mother Elizabeth, he was filled with the Holy Spirit (i.e. baptized in the womb) which caused him to be born without Original Sin.

As the divinely appointed “Precursor” of Jesus Christ, his life was closely intertwined with the earthly life of Jesus. On this feast day of St. John the Baptist we can reflect on how much like Jesus he truly was (www.catholiccompany.com).

Foreword to “Francis Effect”

The episcopal motto of Jorge Mario Bergoglio was *Miserando atque eligendo* (“because he saw him through the eyes of mercy and chose him”). He told me during my interview of 2013: “I always felt it as very true for me”. The motto is taken from the Homilies of St Bede the Venerable. Commenting on the gospel episode of the calling of St Matthew he writes: “Jesus saw a publican and, since he looked at him with a feeling of love, he said: ‘Follow me’.” And he added: “The Latin gerund *miserando* seems to me untranslatable both in Italian and in Spanish. I like to translate it with another gerund: *misericordiando* (‘mercy’).”

For Pope Francis, mercy requires a language that doesn’t exist, it stimulates his linguistic creativity. Here he turns a noun (mercy) into a verb in the form of a gerund (mercying). The Pope loves, in general, verbs more than nouns. The noun refers to the “substance” and has the value of the object, actually, of the thing considered in its fixity. The verb, instead, denotes flow of time, action, dynamism, in a word, experience. Therefore, with this simple linguistic operation Pope Francis wants to say that mercy must lose its fixity of an “act” to become an “action”, that is a “process,” or dynamism. Not “er’gon” (an act, a position, a stand) but *energheia*, energy. Process and energy develop in time. Bergoglio intends the “work” of mercy as an element in an open process, defined by two verbs: loving and building. Work of mercy is never an isolated gesture. Mercy expresses an energy that unfolds in time more than space: it starts the process more than being an isolated and defined fact closed in on itself. And time is greater than space because the development of growth unfolds in a process, in the real life.

Obviously, whoever is merciful is “near” to whomever is nearby, is spatially close, touches him or her. But not only that:

it is he or she who makes space in his or her vital tension. The father of the prodigal son is “merciful” because “while the son was still far away [...], he saw him and he felt compassion”, we read in the gospel parable (cfr Lk 15:11-32). It is a nearness that becomes physical, but before he lives all the temporal tension of the real encounter. The forgiveness precedes the repentance. This is real life.

A friend of mine who has received a personal note from Pope Francis—he was an artist with a troubled life—read to me with emotion these phrases: “God searches for us, God awaits us, God finds us ...before we search for Him, before we expect Him, before we find him. This is the mystery of holiness”. In one of his conversations with Rabbi Abraham Skorka, Bergoglio confessed: “I will say that God is to be found while walking, you look for Him, and He lets you search for Him. They are two paths that meet. For our part, we search for Him pushed by an instinct that is born from the heart. And then we meet, there we realize that He was already searching, that he had preceded us”.

The journey of the Church, and each one of us corresponds to the waiting and to the patience of God. We are speaking of processes — that is of time — not only of egregious gestures tied to a moment. Very often Bergoglio has associated God’s mercy to the image of the journey.

This is also the key to grasp Bergoglio’s vision, to understand his thoughts, gestures, acts, initiatives and voyages. Pope Francis is not solely a Pope who accomplishes acts, but also a Pope who opens processes. Life itself is a journey, a process, a living and open process. Francis wants to avoid every form of ideological approach. And only fidelity to history can save us from ideology, not sure, static objectives or abstract ideas. Mercy has nothing of the static nor of the abstract. It is a virtue in the etymological sense of *virtus*, strength of action.

The editors of this wonderful book on Pope Francis have asked about 51 theologians and Church leaders to reflect on one quote from Pope Francis. The idea here is to make the thoughts of Pope

Francis available to the Indian audience by sharing lived experiences and powerful insights on faith, dignity, family, science, truth, openness and the Church. These experiences and insights come from a living experience, from processes, not from ideas.

Reading this book means to remember that we live in a time period of profound changes. It is usual to say, a period of crisis: educational, economic, ecological, moral... It is possible to do an analysis of the situations and describe them, but we know that the man and woman of today live at a time that poses great challenges. Fear of the new means that some are not able to tolerate uncertainty and he or she shuts down in the face of challenges — real or imagined — that any change brings with itself.

The believer, precisely because he or she keeps hope, now more than ever is called to deal with the social and spiritual processes. Those who contributed to this book feel called to deal with these processes. Here they give their witness in the light of the words of Pope Francis. Reading these pages we conclude that we cannot let ourselves be conquered by doubt, disappointment, or powerlessness. Evangelical spiritual discernment seeks to recognize the sign of the Spirit in the human, social and cultural reality; the seeds already planted by his presence in the events, in the sensibilities, in the desires, in the profound tensions of the heart and of the social, cultural and spiritual contexts. It is an interior attitude that pushes us to be open to dialogue, to encounter, to finding God anywhere. He is to be found and not solely in perimeters narrow or however well-defined and fenced. Above all, don’t fear the ambiguity of life and face it with courage, gathering all the good possible, the positive tensions. Christianity is an enriching and creative interpretation (or hermeneutics) of life and reality.

Antonio Spadaro SJ

Editor in Chief *La Civiltà Cattolica*

Francis Effect: Fifty-One Articles on Pope Francis’ Insights.
Kuruvilla Pandikattu & Vadappuram M Jose (eds) Papal Seminary, Pune, 2018, ISBN: 81-88864-35-8; pp. xxvi+234, ₹ 250.

SNIPPETS FROM POPE FRANCIS

Pope Francis has the uncanny art of unpacking the most from the Scripture. His reflections on the verse: “Where is the child who has been born king of the Jews? For we have observed his star in the East, and have come to worship him” (Mt 2:2).

- The Magi did not set out because they had seen the star, but they saw the star because they had already set out
- They were guided by an inner restlessness. They were open to something new.
- They reflect the image of all those who in their lives have not let their hearts become anesthetized.
- They go to the peripheries, to the frontiers, to places not yet evangelized, to encounter their Lord.
- Nor do they do this out of a sense of superiority, but rather as beggars who cannot ignore the eyes of those who for whom the Good News is still uncharted territory.
- They had to discover that what they sought was not in a palace, but elsewhere, both existentially and geographically.
- Herod is unable to worship because he could not or would not change his own way of looking at things.